

Skills 4 eosc

D3.2 Evidence-based policy and Public Administration training final report

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Deliverable Abstract

This final report presents the outcomes and key insights from the training on Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making. Designed to strengthen the capacity of policymakers, civil servants and knowledge brokers involved in decision making, the training explored how Open Science practices and evidence-informed approaches can enhance policy effectiveness and transparency. The report outlines the processes followed in the design and delivery of the training, including learning objectives, structure, participant engagement and evaluation results. It also includes insights from national sessions held in each participating country, highlighting the training's impact across diverse settings.

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TERMINOLOGY

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALLEA	All European Academies
BBB	BigBlueButton
CC	Competence Centre
CC BY	Creative Commons - Attribution (license)
CUDOS	Communism, Universalism, Disinterestedness, and Organized Skepticism
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EIDM	Evidence-informed Decision Making
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IDCC	International Digital Curation Conference
IP	Intellectual Property
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Centre

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OS	Open Science
OSI	Open Science Infrastructure
QA	Quality Assurance
QAF	Quality Assurance Framework
QRPs	Questionable Research Practices
RDM	Research Data Management
RFO	Research Funding Organization
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RPO	Research Performing Organization
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
S4E	Skills4EOSC
S4P	Science4Policy (Science for Policy)
SAM	Scientific Advice Mechanism (to the European Commission)
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TETTRIs	Transforming European Taxonomy through Training, Research and Innovations
TtT	Train-the-Trainer
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

Executive summary	11
1 Introduction	13
2 Training Programme Design and Methodology	17
2.1 Overview of the Training Approach.....	17
2.2 Methodology for Training Material Development.....	17
3 Overview of Training Modules and Content	25
3.1 Module 01: Fundamentals of Open Science	25
3.2 Module 02: Open Science and Society.....	26
3.3 Module 03: Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation	27
3.4 Module 04: Open Science vs. Closed Science.....	28
3.5 Module 05: Accountability and Transparency in Open Science.....	30
3.6 Module 06: Legal and Ethical Frameworks and Considerations in Open Science	31
3.7 Module 07: Open Science under the EU Data Regulatory Framework	32
3.8 Module 08: Data Governance and Legislative Strategies for FAIR Research.....	32
3.9 Module 09: Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision Making.....	33
3.10 Module 10: Evidence-informed decision making - outputs and tools	35
3.11 Module 11: Open Science and its Stakeholders.....	36
3.12 Module 12: Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders	37
3.13 Module 13: Investing in Open Science	39
3.14 Module 14: Capacity Building and Training Programs in Open Science	40

3.15	Module 15: Open Science and Artificial Intelligence.....	41
3.16	Module 16: Policy making in Open Science.....	42
3.17	Module 17: Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices 43	
3.18	Module 18: Implementing Open Science Policies.....	45
3.19	Module 19: From developing to evaluating Open Science policies	46
3.20	Module 20: Open Science Policies Adaptation	46
4	Training Implementation and Delivery, and Certification	48
4.1	Digital Tools and Content Formats.....	48
4.2	Assessment methods included in the courses	49
4.3	Certification process	51
4.4	Training Delivery Phases.....	55
5	Participation and Engagement	60
6	Feedback, Evaluation and Impact.....	68
6.1	Feedback Collection Process.....	68
6.2	Participant Feedback Analysis.....	69
7	Relevant Additional Material and Events.....	81
7.1	Additional Materials	81
7.2	Relevant Events	87
8	National Pilot Trainings	92
8.1	Overview of the National Pilot Trainings.....	92
8.2	Country Reports on National Pilot Trainings.....	96
8.3	Conclusions/Comparative analysis of the pilots.....	123
8.4	Course Material reused in other cases/trainings.....	126
9	Lessons Learned, Best Practices and Next Steps.....	134
9.1	Lessons Learned.....	134
9.2	Recommendations and Best Practices.....	137

9.3 Next Steps/Suggestions for future activities (beyond the scope of this project).....138

10 Acknowledgements.....140

11 Annexes142

11.1 Annex A. Evaluation Forms.....142

11.2 Annex B. Highlights and Testimonials from course participants.145

Figures

Figure 1: High-level mindmap showing the structure of the deliverable.15

Figure 2: FAIR-by-design methodology17

Figure 3: The cover page of the Learning Path.....57

Figure 4: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Guidelines and Best Practices for Honest Brokers"82

Figure 5: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres"83

Figure 6: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Advancing evidence-based policymaking through Open Collections and Open Science Principles"84

Figure 7: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Guidelines and FAQs on Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI)"85

Figure 8: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Guidelines for Writing a Privacy Policy in Research Projects"86

Figure 9: Photo taken during the stakeholders forum “Empowering Europe's Green Deal: Open Science Skills and Taxonomy for sustainable innovation” panel discussion and setting.....88

Figure 10: Cover and excerpts from the workshop report "Science4policy: bridging the gap between research and decision making"89

Figure 11: Photos taken during Session 4 Group Activity: “Open Science Training Plan Development”90

Figure 12: Skills4EOOSC Poster won “Most Effective” initiative (right) and photo taken during the SAM conference voting process (left)91

Figure 13: Initial indicative timeline for the national pilots93

Tables

Table 1: Initial key messages.....	20
Table 2: Initial key considerations	21
Table 3: Description of Certification Badges created for the EIDM Learning Path	53
Table 4: Content details and Schedule of Pilot TtT trainings	56
Table 5: Content Details per Course and Schedule of live sessions in both rounds	58
Table 6: Total number of participation per course across both rounds. Including number of badges awarded.	61
Table 7: Top 10 Countries by Attendance for Round 1, across all 7 courses.	62
Table 8: Top 10 Countries by Attendance in Round 2, across all 7 courses.	64
Table 9: Total views per course for Round 2.	66
Table 10: Course release timeline from March to June 2025.	66
Table 11: Number of Responses received by participants per round	68
Table 12: Initial Plan for the National Pilots	92
Table 13: Actual Structure of National Pilots	93
Table 14: National Pilots Analysis Summary Table	123

Executive summary

The *D3.2 Evidence-based Policy and Public Administration Training Final Report* presents the outcomes of the Train-the-Trainer programme designed to strengthen the capacity of trainers to be able to deliver Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making (EIDM) training to policymakers, civil servants and knowledge brokers. The programme aimed to improve policy effectiveness, transparency and trust by equipping participants with practical skills and knowledge.

Programme Design and Scope

The curriculum comprised seven courses, organised into 20 modules and 45 lectures, delivered in three phases: one pilot and two full rounds. The report outlines the training's design, delivery, and evaluation, and the use of digital badges for certification.

Participation and Engagement

- **Enrolments and Geographical Coverage:** 805 total enrolments, representing 180 unique participants from 27 countries and 102 organisations.
- **Certification:** 118 successful course completions in Round 1 and 190 in Round 2.
- **Engagement:** Round 2 materials received 30,903 views.

National Pilots

- **Participation:** 18 national pilots delivered in 15 countries, training approximately 640 participants, exceeding participation goals and material reach.
- **Formats:** 11 in-person, 7 online events; delivery languages included English, mixed, and national languages.

Impact and Feedback

Participant feedback was highly positive, with participants highlighting the quality, structure and relevance of the content and delivery. Many reported increased confidence in both applying the knowledge and delivering training.

Conclusions

The Train-the-Trainer initiative demonstrated strong engagement, high satisfaction and adaptability across contexts, which highlights a strong potential for scalable capacity building, enabling trainers from multiple disciplines to reach target audiences related to Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making, such as policymakers, civil servants and knowledge brokers.

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the methodology, development, implementation, and evaluation of the **“Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” Learning Path**, a targeted training initiative designed under the Skills4EOSC project for **policymakers, civil servants, and knowledge brokers**. The learning path addresses the pressing need to equip these professional profiles with the knowledge, skills, and competences to engage with and apply Open Science principles in policy development and evidence-informed decision making.

This training pathway is **not a general-purpose curriculum** but one tailored to the distinctive needs and roles of policy sector professionals. Recognising that little existing training material fully addressed these profiles, the development process combined a **landscaping analysis of relevant initiatives** with the **creation of original, purpose-built content**. The goal was to ensure that the training program **responds directly to the real-world responsibilities, constraints, and opportunities** faced by decision-makers and intermediaries in public administrations.

The training was designed using the **FAIR-by-design methodology** and anchored in the **Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) framework** developed in Skills4EOSC. This helped to identify learning needs and formulate **key messages and learning outcomes** aligned with the target professional profiles and their required competences.

Section 2 outlines the **methodology followed** for identifying training needs, defining key messages and learning outcomes, and selecting or developing content specifically tailored to the profiles of policymakers, civil servants, and knowledge brokers. It provides a summarised overview of the content and process described in greater detail in *D3.1 Policy makers and civil servants training plan*¹, emphasising how the training design was informed by profile-specific competences and contextual requirements.

¹ Anastasopoulou, N., Evangelinou, B., Bjerde, K. W., Bjonnes, L., Filiposka, S., Green, D., Sánchez Moreno, M., Giglia, E., Prnjat, O., Di Giorgio, S., & Lazzeri, E. (2024). D3.1 Policy makers and civil servants training plan (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14797111>

Section 3 provides a **comprehensive overview of the training curriculum**, focusing on the specific modules and content derived by the process presented in section 2. The training curriculum is divided into a series of modules, each targeting specific learning outcomes, and is designed to gradually build participants' competences.

Section 4 outlines the **implementation and delivery process** for the training program. The training was delivered in three main phases: pilot sessions and rounds 1 and 2, designed to engage participants progressively and assess the effectiveness of the curriculum at each stage. This section also describes the **assessment and certification framework** for the training program. It outlines the methods used to evaluate participants' understanding and progress throughout the course, as well as analyses the certification process followed for this specific learning path, detailing how participants' achievements are recognised upon successful completion.

Section 5 focuses on the **level of participation and engagement** throughout the training, demonstrating the reach and impact of the learning path. It presents participation data across countries and organisations, reflecting the diverse professional backgrounds of learners, from university staff to national research infrastructure experts. The analysis briefly explores course completion rates, and volume of certification awards. Overall, it showcases the richness of the Skill4EOSC network and its utilisation provided a robust and engaged audience. **Section 6** focuses on **feedback and evaluation**. It describes the processes used to gather feedback from participants throughout the training, including post-session surveys and ongoing evaluations. The section highlights how this feedback was used to assess the effectiveness of the training materials and delivery methods. It also explains how the feedback informed improvements in each round, ensuring that the training remained relevant and effective. Finally, this section explores the broader outcomes of the training, such as changes in participants' attitudes toward evidence-informed decision-making and their potential to apply the knowledge gained in their professional contexts.

Section 7 presents **additional resources and relevant events** that supported the training learning path. The additional resources include

booklets and materials developed in the other tasks of the work package, which were used within the courses as supplementary readings to deepen participants' understanding on different topics. The section also highlights relevant events, such as training workshops, dissemination activities, and stakeholder engagement sessions, which helped promote the training, provide additional knowledge on certain topics, share the project outcomes, and encourage the broader adoption of Open Science and evidence-informed practices in decision making.

Section 8 provides an **overview of the national pilot trainings on policy**, where the training materials developed during the Train-the-Trainer (TtT) sessions were adapted and delivered in national contexts to train local relevant communities. The focus of these pilots was to empower communities in the field of decision-making at the national level with the skills and knowledge needed for Open Science and evidence-informed decision making. This section highlights how the training content was used in a local context, details the approach taken in each country, as well as the results achieved in terms of participant engagement and impact.

Section 9 focuses on the **lessons learned and best practices** derived from the implementation of the "Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making" training programme. It explores key insights gained throughout the training process, highlighting successful strategies and areas for improvement. This section serves as a reflection on the overall training approach and the experiences encountered, offering valuable guidance for future implementations.

Finally, **section 10** contains the list of all contributors to the training events and activities, who have been fundamental for the success of these activities and therefore deserve a huge thanks.

Figure 1: High-level mind map showing the structure of the deliverable.

2 Training Programme Design and Methodology

2.1 Overview of the Training Approach

Deliverable *D3.1 Policy makers and civil servants training plan* provides the full approach that was planned to be followed in order to develop the training material for the learning path on “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” (EIDM), tailored to the needs of the professional profiles of policy makers, civil servants and knowledge brokers.

In this section we will provide a short summary of this work that was initially presented in D3.1 and was followed for the design and development of the training material and delivery of the courses, with some additional updates.

2.2 Methodology for Training Material Development

This subsection presents the methodology used to develop the training materials, focusing on the FAIR-by-design approach, the identification of training needs and competences through the Minimum Viable Skillsets framework, and the key messages guiding content creation. It also outlines the quality assurance process that ensured the training materials’ relevance and effectiveness for the target audience.

2.2.1 FAIR-by-design Methodology

As previously highlighted in D3.1, the FAIR-by-design approach delivered by WP2 was followed. The methodology for FAIR-by-design learning materials is described in *D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials*², with final recommendations outlined in *MS2.4 Final recommendations on FAIR-by-Design training resources*³. The FAIR-by-design methodology provides a

² Filiposka, S., et al. (2023). D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305540>.

³ Filiposka, S., et al (2025). MS2.4 - Final recommendations on FAIR-by-Design training resources. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930618>.

comprehensive framework for the development of learning materials, offering clear, structured guidance on how to create FAIR training resources whilst being flexible with the choice of tools, platforms and content formats. The methodology aims to empower the popular backward instructional design process with additional activities related to the creation of FAIR learning materials from both, the perspective of trainers aiming for future reuse, and the trainees requiring easy access and usability. Within D2.2, a detailed step-by-step workflow (see Fig. 1) is outlined, guiding the training material designers through all the phases of the material preparation process, while ensuring the final result will adhere to the FAIR principles.

FAIR-by-design Methodology

Figure 2: FAIR-by-design methodology

As presented in the FAIR-by-design methodology, the main goal was not to start from scratch with the creation of the training materials needed in WP3, but aimed to reuse existing training materials in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) community as much as possible, while adhering to the intellectual property rights (IPR) implications. Following the methodology also ensured that the training materials used by the trainers were well structured, described using a common metadata schema, and properly licensed for reuse outside the project, while also adhering to a collective quality assurance process. The methodology also incorporates guidance on

the creation of not only the learning content, but also the accompanying materials that aim to facilitate their use by trainers, including information on the training organisation, assessment and feedback gathering.

Finally, adopting the FAIR-by-design methodology ensured that the training materials developed for the TtT events included all necessary information needed to successfully organise the national pilot training events, discussed later in this report. Similarly, the FAIR-by-design methodology process can be followed when adapting and localising the TtT learning materials for each country.

2.2.2 Identifying Training Needs and Competences

A main priority of Skills4EOSC is to define a catalogue of Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) for different EOSC actors and Open Science practitioners, including researchers, various professional roles that support them, policy makers and other stakeholders. The MVS is a key resource for the project's core objective of advancing Open Science (OS) in each related professional profile.

A Skills4EOSC MVS describes essential skills and competences required to deliver OS outcomes for communities and organisations. The development of the MVS were first outlined in a Skills4EOSC deliverable, *D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles – Minimum Viable Skillsets*.⁴ An MVS is associated with a profile that gives additional context by describing the OS mission and outcomes typically expected from the role, the activities involved in contributing to those outcomes, and the proficiency level needed for each of the essential skills. While each MVS is role-specific, the roles are described at a broad level with the aim of accommodating alternative titles, for example all 'data professional' roles share a similar mission for Open Science.

A key use case for the MVS is for trainers to learn about and determine which skills their learners will need to develop for the Open Science role(s) their

⁴ Whyte, A., Green, D., Avanço, K., Di Giorgio, S., Gingold, A., Horton, L., Koteska, B., Kyprianou, K., Prnjat, O., Rauste, P., Schirru, L., Sowinski, C., Torres Ramos, G., van Leersum, N., Sharma, C., Méndez, E., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101903>

training needs to target.⁵ The MVS is intended to be an evolving “plan”, rather than a final product, as:

- it encapsulates what a person needs to learn, or be trained in, to be able to perform their role and contribute to the desired outcomes for Open Science,
- it summarises essential skills and maps them to standard terms for skills and competences, such as the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO),
- by making explicit the trainers’ assumptions about the learners’ context, it can help determine the training needs for each role, and develop courses that meet those needs,
- and serves as a resource for an ongoing conversation that trainers need to have about learning objectives for Open Science with other trainers, with people in the roles they are targeting, and with other stakeholders, such as policymakers and leaders at their organisations.

In Skills4EOOSC, various work packages like WP3 have used the MVS to inform their work on training and curriculum development. This has provided the project with a unique opportunity to explore how the MVS informs training, but also use the experience of training WPs to better align the MVS content and design to the training needs in the different WPs.

2.2.3 Key Messages and Considerations

The development of key messages and considerations for the EIDM training was firmly grounded in the MVS framework. As mentioned above, this framework provided a structured way to identify the essential competences and skills required by policymakers, civil servants and knowledge brokers to effectively engage with Open Science and evidence-informed decision making and address both gaps and emerging needs within the policy environment.

⁵ The second iteration of the MVS Catalogue – D2.6 Catalogue of OS career profiles and MVS - update is available from 30 June 2025 at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15731870>. It describes in detail how the MVS can be used to inform training.

Therefore, building on the MVS analysis, the team formulated a set of clear and targeted key messages that would serve as a foundation for the training content. Additionally, contextual considerations were integrated to ensure that the training was meaningful in diverse policy and public administration settings. This alignment between competences and skills, messages, and context was critical to create a focused and impactful learning experience.

In Tables 1 and 2 below, we provide the initial key messages and key considerations that were discussed in D3.1 and that guided the development of the training material of the learning path, in addition to the MVS.

Table 1: Initial key messages

No.	Key Message
01	Open Science is essential for advancing research and innovation
02	Open Science is the new normal
03	Open Science is a multi-stakeholder endeavour
04	Open Science leads to more transparency, reproducibility, reliability and accountability
05	There are challenges to implementing Open Science, but there are ways to overcome them
06	Policy plays a critical role in supporting Open Science
07	What can Policy Makers do for Open Science to succeed?
08	Policy makers need to invest in new competences in Open Science and related professional profiles and careers
09	There are costs associated with not supporting Open Science and FAIR management of research outputs
10	Policy makers / civil servants can make use of Open Science outputs for evidence-based decisions
11	There are many successful examples of real-life scientific topics with high societal impact of use Open Science in policy making.
12	Public organisations should develop strategies for implementing Open Science policies
13	Scientists' engagement is key to effective and equitable evidence-informed decision-making
14	Ethical, Legal and Societal issues are central to support Open Science and can be found in most of the messages above. As an example, a well-tailored, balanced, Intellectual Property legal framework is a key factor to foster innovation, access and re-use, and incentivize creators
15	Open Science-positive policies can become the catalyst for change in reward and hiring practices, as well as responsible research assessment

Table 2: Initial key considerations

No.	Considerations
01	Am I collecting and documenting data systematically with accompanying metadata for future reference?
02	Have I considered privacy concerns while handling sensitive data and adhered to legal and ethical standards?
03	How can I facilitate collaboration by sharing non-sensitive data and advocating for open data platforms?
04	Am I staying updated on evolving Open Science practices and adopting new technologies for data management?
05	How can I foster collaborative relationships with other government agencies to promote Open Science?
06	How can I communicate data to the public in accessible ways for evidence-based policy making?
07	Am I staying informed about best practices and training opportunities related to Open Science and data management?
08	How can I advocate for Open Science practices and inspire colleagues to embrace transparency?
09	How can I uphold ethical principles throughout data collection, sharing and use in my daily work?
10	How Open Science and data management can be used in different fields of public administration?

These initial key messages and key considerations were elaborated into numerous modules, based on specific learning objectives and outcomes included in the training. The full curriculum of the Learning Path on “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” is provided in section 3, along with an analysis of the specific learning objectives per module and lecture.

2.2.4 Quality Assurance Process

The quality assurance process ensured the relevance and coherence of the training materials in two main steps. First, an internal review committee was established within the task members to confirm that the content was tailored to the target audience. Second, the Quality Assurance Framework (QAF) of the project was applied to improve overall quality of the courses and reusability of the course materials, throughout the development process.

2.2.4.1 Internal Review Committee

To maintain relevance, accuracy and usability of the course materials, an internal review committee was established within the task team. This committee was composed of experienced project members with strong expertise in Open Science, evidence-informed decision making, and instructional design, and also familiar with the target audience and their needs. The main role of this committee was to review each lecture in every module and evaluate its relevance to the target audience, its content accuracy and clarity, and its alignment with the learning objectives and pedagogical soundness. Feedback was collected from the committee and communicated to content developers, who revised the material accordingly.

The involvement of the Internal Review Committee significantly enhanced the overall quality of the training material. It provided a structured mechanism to detect and correct gaps or inconsistencies early, as well as to avoid duplication of material between different lectures. It also ensured that the final content was robust, contextually relevant and learner-centred.

2.2.4.2 Quality Assurance Framework

The S4E Quality Assurance Framework (S4E-QAF) is a practical, community-informed tool developed in Task 2.4⁶ to improve the quality, coherence, and reusability of Open Science learning materials. Its purpose is to guide course creators through the key quality aspects of instructional design, ensuring that Open Science training is not only about Open Science, but also developed and delivered according to Open Science principles. The QAF is structured around four sub-frameworks: Essential, Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS), FAIR-by-design, and Ethical, Legal, and Societal Implications (ELSI).

Each indicator within the framework is classified by two levels of compliance (minimal and detailed) and supports continuous improvement through maturity levels, from Level 1 (informal awareness) to Level 4 (optimised, sustainable QA processes).

⁶ Sánchez Moreno, M., Green, D., Filiposka, S., Winandi, A., & Drązewski, K. (2025). D2.7 Community-endorsed quality assurance and certification framework for professional training and qualifications - final version. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15731878>

WP3 TtT courses were designed and delivered with a step-by-step application of the QAF across three key stages:

Initial QA Awareness – Checklist & Guide (Maturity Level 1 to 2)

In the early design phase, WP3 course designers used the interactive QAF Checklist & Guide to self-reflect on course structure and quality. This helped identify initial gaps, particularly around metadata, licensing clarity, and learner-centred goals. The focus at this stage was on understanding the QAF and aligning the course with minimal compliance.

First Evaluation Round – Evaluation & Feedback Spreadsheets (Maturity Level 2 to 3)

Once the first versions (rounds) of the TtT courses were delivered, a structured two-way evaluation was conducted using QAF spreadsheets. Both the course team and Task 2.4 partners assessed the courses independently.

This allowed cross-verification and identification of consistent misalignments (e.g. in metadata use, certification clarity, and keyword tagging). Feedback was provided through comments and best practices, which the WP3 team used to revise content and improve compliance with both minimal and detailed indicators.

Final Evaluation – S4E Quality Compass App (Maturity Level 3 to 4)

After implementing suggested improvements from the 1st round evaluation stage, the WP3 course team used the S4E Quality Compass web app for a full self-assessment. The app provided an instant, structured report summarising their performance across sections and sub-frameworks. The final score and recommendations supported a transition to maturity level 4, representing a fully compliant, reviewed, and optimised training resource.

Through this staged application of the QAF, the WP3 team not only improved course quality but also contributed to refining the framework itself—demonstrating how the QAF can serve as both a guidance tool and evaluation method in Open Science training.

3 Overview of Training Modules and Content

This section provides an overview of the training modules developed for the Learning Path on “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision-Making” (EIDM). The Learning Path comprises seven courses, divided into a total of 20 modules. Each module includes one or more lectures, amounting to 45 lectures overall. The aim of each module is provided below, along with the specific learning objectives for each individual lecture.

3.1 Module 01: Fundamentals of Open Science

Aims of the module: Provide learners with a comprehensive overview of Open Science, focusing on its core values and principles, including the application of FAIR principles to promote transparency, reusability and collaboration in research.

Lecture 1: Open Science values and principles

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Provide a definition of Open Science, including access to the products of scientific research and participation in the process of knowledge production.
- Outline the core values, principles, and pillars of Open Science, using the UNESCO framework.⁷

Lecture 2: FAIR Principles and their role in Open Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Provide a definition of the FAIR data principles and explain how to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in practice.

⁷ UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.2021. CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO license. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949> and UNESCO Open Science Toolkit. 2023. CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO license. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000387983>

- Explain the importance of metadata and unique persistent identifiers in making data FAIR.

3.2 Module 02: Open Science and Society

Aims of the module: Explore the societal and economic impacts of Open Science and citizen science, examining historical and contemporary examples that illustrate their significance in addressing societal challenges and enhancing public engagement.

Lecture 1: Societal and Economic impact of Citizen Science from Galileo to post-truth populism

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain the historical development of Open Science and citizen science, from Galileo's era to the present day, and their importance in contemporary scientific practices.
- Analyse the impact of post-truth populism on the scientific community and the necessity of preserving objectivity and expertise in science communication.
- Evaluate the application of Merton's CUDOS (Communism, Universalism, Disinterestedness, and Organized Skepticism) norms in citizen science to ensure rigorous, expert-led contributions by non-experts.

Lecture 2: Societal Impact of Open Science - Real-life examples

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Describe relevant examples from various scientific domains of the impact of Open Science initiatives on society.
- Explain how Open Science practices contributed to the benefit of society in various areas, i.e. health research and healthcare, humanitarian actions, environment, climate change, social sciences and humanities.
- Identify the most suitable examples for the training activities they are going to do in their own environment.

- Discuss with their prospective target audience (e.g., policymakers, educators, or other stakeholders) how Open Science can benefit society by means of real examples.

Activity⁸: Exploring the Impact of Open Science

Objective: In the lectures of Modules 2 and 3, various examples illustrating the impact of open science on society were discussed. These examples span a range of scientific and societal areas, showcasing how open science initiatives can foster innovation, improve public trust in research, and enhance collaborative efforts. The goal of this activity is to deepen the participants understanding of the significance of open science by exploring specific examples and preparing to communicate their relevance to a target audience.

3.3 Module 03: Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation

Aims of the module: highlight the critical role of Open Science in fostering scientific progress and innovation by examining its benefits and practical applications in research.

Lecture 1: Open Science: Benefits for scientific progress

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Analyse how Open Science accelerates scientific progress by enhancing transparency, reusability, reproducibility, and collaboration among researchers.
- Evaluate the societal and scientific benefits of open access to research resources, such as publications, data, and educational materials, in fostering equity and inclusion.

Lecture 2: Open Science in Practice

⁸ Note: This document presents only the objective of the activities. The full instructions and detailed guidance for implementing each activity are provided in the course material.

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Discuss real-world examples of Open Science initiatives and their impact on advancing research, collaboration, and innovation.
- Explain how Open Science practices enhance transparency, accessibility, reusability and reproducibility in large-scale scientific projects such as the Human Genome Project, Large Hadron Collider, and OpenStreetMap.
- Evaluate the role of FAIR data sharing in global scientific discoveries, with examples from fields such as genomics, particle physics, and astronomy.
- Analyse how platforms and initiatives like PLOS, ENCODE, and EOSC promote interdisciplinary collaboration, FAIR data-sharing policies, and public engagement in scientific research.

3.4 Module 04: Open Science vs. Closed Science

Aims of the module: critically examine the differences between open and closed science by exploring the historical context, ethical challenges, economic impacts, and the importance of fostering a culture of openness in research.

Lecture 1: Closed Science - A Historical Perspective and Negative Consequences

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain the purpose of science and the importance of open exchange of knowledge and ideas for scientific progress.
- Analyse key features of Closed Science and contrast them with Open Science.
- Explain the dominance of Closed Science practices from the ancient and medieval times to the present day and reflect on the reasons why Closed Science persists.
- List the negative impacts of Closed Science.

- Explain the concept of Closed-Science-to-Open-Science continuum and the steps that research organisations can take to move toward Open Science.

Lecture 2: Challenges and Ethical Dilemmas in Closed Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Analyse the ethical dilemmas associated with closed science, including its implications for research integrity and public trust in scientific findings.
- Evaluate various scenarios depicting the practical costs of closed science, assessing their impact on innovation, collaboration, and societal advancement.

Activity: Case study on Ethical Dilemmas in Closed Science.

Objective: In this activity, participants analyse a real-world case where closed science practices led to ethical dilemmas. Through this exercise, they reflect on how Open Science principles could have mitigated these challenges and propose practical solutions. The goal of this activity is to critically examine ethical dilemmas associated with closed science and to explore how open science practices can address these issues, improving transparency and societal benefit.

Lecture 3: The Economic Impact of Closed Science vs Open Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify and describe the key economic benefits of Open Science, including faster innovation, cost reduction, and job creation.
- Explain how Open Science promotes global collaboration among researchers and its significance both on inclusion and in addressing complex challenges.
- Discuss the role of Open Science in enhancing access to educational resources and its impact on workforce development.

- Analyse the implications of Open Science on resource distribution, focusing on its potential to promote equity and inclusivity in scientific research.

Lecture 4: Building a Culture of Openness

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Describe the key strategies policy makers can use to build a culture of openness in scientific organisations and overcome resistance to change.
- Identify the importance of training, education and awareness in promoting Open Science practices among researchers, institutions, and the public.
- Discuss some main challenges and barriers to implementing Open Science practices, including cultural resistance, data privacy concerns, and the need for adequate training and infrastructure.

3.5 Module 05: Accountability and Transparency in Open Science

Aims of the module: emphasise the importance of accountability and transparency in Open Science by examining strategies to foster research integrity and enhance reproducibility in scientific practices.

Lecture 1: Fostering Research Integrity and Reproducibility

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Provide definition of research misconduct and identify three main types (fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism).
- Identify the most common types of Questionable Research Practices (QRPs) and give examples.
- Explain how a focus on research transparency, accountability, and integrity can help reduce research misconduct and improve reproducibility.

3.6 Module 06: Legal and Ethical Frameworks and Considerations in Open Science

Aims of the module: provide an understanding of the legal and ethical considerations in Open Science by examining the regulatory framework and key ethical issues that arise in the context of open research practices.

Lecture 1: Overview of the legal regulatory framework on Personal Data, Non-Personal Data and Intellectual Property

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain the key goals of the EU's data strategy.
- Describe the Open Data Directive and its impact on public data reuse.
- Recognise the importance of data protection in the EU's legal framework

Lecture 2: Landscaping Ethical Issues in Open Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain the Relationship Between Law and Ethics in Open Science.
- Analyse the Ethical Principles Guiding Open Science Practices.
- Assess Ethical Risks in Open Science Policies and Their Legal Implications.

Activity: I, AI - Ethical Debates and Policy Decisions for the EU In the light of the Development of Conscious AI.

Objective: Based on fictional case studies, participants build a strong argument on the ethical, social, and legal aspects of deploying conscious AI in the EU. The primary goal of this activity is to engage participants in a structured ethical, social, and legal analysis of emerging AI technologies by challenging them to develop and defend policy positions in a simulated policy debate. Through this, participants will critically evaluate the implications of fostering or restricting conscious AI development in the EU, considering ethical theories, fundamental rights, regulatory frameworks, and data governance concerns.

3.7 Module 07: Open Science under the EU Data Regulatory Framework

Aims of the module: Explore the distinctions and regulatory considerations for handling non-personal and personal data in Open Science.

Lecture 1: Open Science and Non-personal Data

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain the EU Legal Framework on Non-Personal Data.
- Analyse the Role of Intellectual Property Rights in Open Science.
- Explore Copyright and Its Impact on Open Science.

Lecture 2: Personal Data in Open Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Analyse the limitations imposed by personal data on Open Science activities.
- Discuss the ethical considerations and principles that must be adhered to in research involving personal data.

Additional Reading: Guidelines and FAQs on Ethical, Legal and Social Issues. A description is provided in *section 7.1.4*.

3.8 Module 08: Data Governance and Legislative Strategies for FAIR Research

Aims of the module: explore the governance and legislative frameworks necessary for FAIR data practices, focusing on strategies for planning data FAIRification and identifying practical tools to implement FAIR principles effectively.

Lecture 1: Planning the FAIRification of data

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Recognise the key components of Research Data Management necessary for FAIR data practices.
- Summarise the European policies and frameworks that guide data governance and sharing.
- Recognise the importance of creating a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP) to ensure effective research data governance.

Lecture 2: Identifying practical "how to" tools to go FAIR

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Evaluate the components and tools necessary for FAIR data compliance
- Analyse how to apply practical methodologies for FAIR data assessment and governance.

Additional Reading: Guidelines for Writing a Privacy Policy in Research Projects. A description is provided in *section 7.1.5*.

Additional Reading: Guidelines and Best Practices for Honest Brokers Booklet. A description is provided in *section 7.1.1*.

3.9 Module 09: Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision Making

Aims of the module: Introduce the process and practice of Evidence-informed Decision-Making.

Lecture 1: Policy, Evidence and Evidence-Informed Decision Making

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify the key stages in the policy development process and discuss the types of evidence relevant to each stage.

- Analyse key benefits and challenges of evidence-informed policymaking, and assess the importance of balancing evidence with context, values, and feasibility in effective policy outcomes.
- Examine how evidence-informed approaches support ethical standards, objectivity, and accountability within the policymaking process.

Lecture 2: Stakeholders involved in Evidence-Informed Decision Making

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify the key stakeholders involved in evidence-informed decision making and distinguish among their roles and their unique contributions and limitations within science-policy interactions.
- Analyse how different stakeholders contribute to the science-policy interface.

Activity: Exploring the Role of Honest Brokers in Real-Life Decision Making

Objective: The objective of this activity is to analyse the role of honest brokers in real-world decision-making processes, focusing on their challenges, strategies, and impact. By examining a case study on collaborative water planning in New Zealand, participants will critically assess the practical application of knowledge brokerage and reflect on how Open Science principles could enhance the effectiveness of honest brokers in bridging the gap between science and policy.

Activity: Reflecting on Key Challenges

Objective: The objective of this activity is to familiarise with the key challenges Honest Brokers and other professional figures at the interface between science and policy face in their mediation work, and identify potential strategies to cope with them.

3.10 Module 10: Evidence-informed decision making - outputs and tools

Aims of the module: equip participants with the knowledge and tools to effectively integrate Open Science outputs, data science algorithms, and statistical insights into evidence-informed decision-making processes.

Lecture 1: Open Science Outputs in Decision-Making

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify the key components and types of Open Science outputs and their significance in evidence-based decision making.

Lecture 2: Data Science Algorithms in Practice

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain essential terms such as "Open Science," "machine learning," and "data science."
- Describe the process of data analysis in Open Science.
- Analyse the utilisation of the decision tree model for classifying a simple dataset.
- Compare the advantages and disadvantages of various machine learning models.
- Evaluate a machine learning model's performance using metrics like accuracy and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

Lecture 3: Interpreting Statistics for Insights

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain the purpose and application of common data science algorithms like regression and decision trees.

- Interpret a simple data science project involving data analysis and visualisation to communicate findings.

Live Demo Activity⁹: Data Science Tutorial for Policy Makers

Objective: This hands-on training activity is designed to introduce participants to the practical applications of data science in policy-making, using a variety of datasets and analytical techniques. It is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of how data-driven insights can inform policy decisions, making it an invaluable experience for policy makers looking to leverage data science in their work.

3.11 Module 11: Open Science and its Stakeholders

Aims of the module: explore the key stakeholders in Open Science and their roles in shaping its practices, policies, and impact.

Lecture 1: Open Science Stakeholders

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify the diverse stakeholders involved in Open Science, including their roles, responsibilities, and how they contribute to promoting Open Science practices.
- Analyse the specific benefits and challenges that different stakeholder groups face in adopting and promoting Open Science.

Activity: Organise a "Coffee with Open Science" Session

Objective: These sessions focus on presenting work and exchanging ideas on key issues that can shape policy decisions. In this activity, participants take on the role of organising a "Coffee with Open Science" session. The objective of this activity is to develop participants' ability to facilitate policy discussions on Open Science by organising a stakeholder-driven engagement session. Participants will practice identifying relevant stakeholders, justifying

⁹ Note: The Live Demo activities were only used for the purposes of the live sessions.

their inclusion, and structuring a discussion that contributes to informed policy drafting.

3.12 Module 12: Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders

Aims of the module: The aim of this module is to explore effective collaboration strategies for stakeholders in Open Science, focusing on building a collaborative culture, enhancing impact, and fostering communication across research, policy, and public sectors.

Lecture 1: Creating a Collaborative Culture

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Evaluate the role of collaboration in fostering Open Science, drawing on examples such as the Pistoia Alliance and the COVID-19 response to identify key strategies for engagement between science and society.
- Construct a framework for creating a collaborative culture in their own contexts by integrating lessons learned from successful partnerships in Open Science and evidence-informed policymaking.

Lecture 2: Collaboration Impact

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Analyse the limitations of traditional metrics, such as Impact Factor, and propose alternative indicators that reflect the societal impact of research.
- Assess successful case studies of open and collaborative science initiatives, such as VODAN Africa¹⁰, to understand how they effectively address real-world challenges and promote community engagement.

Lecture 3: Case studies of successful collaboration on Open Science

Learning objectives:

¹⁰ <https://aun.mu.edu.et/vodan/>

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Analyse the role of collaboration among stakeholders, using the EOSC Nordic and the NI4OS projects as case studies to illustrate advancements in Open Science.

Lecture 4: Role of Open Science in fostering collaboration among researchers, practitioners, and the public

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify the benefits of Open Science for collaboration among researchers, practitioners, and the public.
- Analyse the challenges to effective collaboration between researchers and practitioners within the Open Science framework.

Additional Reading: “Science4policy: bridging the gap between research and decision making” Workshop. A description is provided in *section 7.2.2*.

Activity: Guidelines for communication with policy makers

Objective: In this activity, participants practice crafting effective communication strategies for engaging with policymakers, using a three-step approach based on the work of Paul Cairney and Richard Kwiatkowski. The objective of this activity is to develop participants’ ability to craft clear, persuasive, and policy-relevant messages tailored to different policymaker audiences. By applying this structured three-step approach, participants will practice framing evidence-based recommendations in a way that resonates with decision-makers, considering timing, audience, and strategic communication techniques.

Lecture 5: Communicating Uncertainty

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Understand and recognise the different types of uncertainty inherent to scientific research and its outputs.

- Identify key factors influencing the communication of uncertainty in various contexts, enhancing their understanding of how uncertainty affects decision-making.
- Apply a structured framework for analysing these factors and effectively conveying uncertainty to diverse audiences, ensuring clarity and understanding in their communication strategies.

Activity: Role Play - Focus on... Verbal communication of uncertainty in practice

Objective: This role-play exercise challenges participants to think critically about how to communicate research findings that contain significant uncertainties. Participants will assume different stakeholder roles and practice communicating these uncertainties to diverse audiences, focusing on verbal communication strategies.

Lecture 6: Data Visualisation and Storytelling

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Apply data visualisation techniques to effectively convey insights to policymakers and stakeholders.
- Construct engaging narratives that integrate data storytelling to foster understanding and inspire action.

3.13 Module 13: Investing in Open Science

Aims of the module: explore how strategic investments and funding mechanisms can promote the adoption and sustainability of Open Science practices.

Lecture 1: The role of funding in promoting Open Science practices

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Recognise the impact of national and international Open Science policies and funding frameworks as models for equitable and sustainable research practices.
- Identify key components of successful Open Science funding policies, including infrastructure support, policy monitoring, and collaborative efforts among funders.
- Explore examples of effective national and international Open Science funding frameworks, such as those in Germany, France, and Spain, to highlight diverse approaches.

Activity: Advocating for Open Science

Objective: This activity focuses on crafting compelling arguments to promote Open Science to funders, using material from the Skills4EOSC Advocacy Kit¹¹, that was developed in WP8. Through self-paced preparation, group collaboration, and role-play, participants learn to identify funder priorities, to adapt key messages and effectively communicate the value of Open Science.

3.14 Module 14: Capacity Building and Training Programs in Open Science

Aims of the module: examine the importance of capacity building and training programs in advancing Open Science, highlighting strategies, tools, and best practices for equipping researchers, institutions, and policymakers with the skills and knowledge to foster Open Science practices.

Lecture 1: Understanding Capacity Building in Open Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify key challenges and considerations in capacity building for Open Science.

¹¹ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/resources/advocacy-kit>

- Evaluate various training formats for Open Science capacity building and assess how these approaches can address the diverse needs of different professionals.

Lecture 2: Institutional Support for Capacity Building – Challenges and Best Practices

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify and analyse key challenges and considerations in building Open Science capacity.
- Evaluate the structure and role of digital competence centres in Open Science capacity building through a case study of the Netherlands.

Activity: Sharing Best Practices and Challenges in Open Science Capacity Building

Objective: This activity aims to encourage participants to reflect on Open Science capacity-building initiatives in their institutions, organisations, or countries. By sharing examples, analysing their impact, and relating them to the case study of the Netherlands, the aim is to foster peer-to-peer learning and identify transferable strategies and challenges.

3.15 Module 15: Open Science and Artificial Intelligence

Aims of the module: explore how AI technologies can advance Open Science practices and evidence-informed decision making, while addressing the ethical, technical, and policy challenges that arise.

Lecture 1: Introduction to AI

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Explain the basic concepts and definitions of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning, and describe their role in enabling AI systems to solve problems autonomously.

Lecture 2: AI and Open Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Examine the infrastructural and computational resources required to support AI systems for Open Science, including supercomputing, data integration, and scalable web services.
- Analyse the benefits and challenges of using AI in Open Science, focusing on sustainability, transparency, and the "black box" nature of AI systems.

Lecture 3: AI in evidence-informed decision making

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Evaluate the practical applications of AI tools in evidence-informed decision-making across diverse domains.
- Identify the limitations and ethical challenges of AI in decision-making.

Live Demo Activity: Prompt Engineering

Objective: This hands-on activity uses an online interactive educational tool designed to introduce policy makers and learners to the fundamentals of artificial intelligence (AI) and data science, with a focus on real-world policy applications.

3.16 Module 16: Policy making in Open Science

Aims of the module: provide an understanding of the principles, development, and significance of Open Science policies in fostering transparency and innovation.

Lecture 1: Introduction to Open Science Policies

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Define the concept of an Open Science policy.

- Clarify the goals and objectives of Open Science policy-making.
- Examine examples of Open Science Policies.

Activity: Analysing an Open Science Policy

Objective: Participants select and analyse an Open Science policy from an institution, government, or funding body of their own choosing, using insights from the *EOSC-Nordic deliverable D2.8: Open Science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries*¹². This exercise will help them identify included and missing Open Science elements, assess gaps or strengths, and reflect on how these insights could apply to their own institution.

3.17 Module 17: Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices

Aims of the module: explore how Open Science policies enable and support the adoption of Open Science practices in research and innovation.

Lecture 1: Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices: Stakeholders

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Give examples of how Open Science policies support and foster Open Science practices.
- Describe the role of different stakeholders in Open Science policy development and implementation.

Activity: Case studies of Open Science policy development and implementation

¹² Hansson, E.-L., Bukauskas, L., Garavelli, S., Gunnarsdóttir, B., Hammargren, P.-O., Rosti, T., Hienola, A., Iozzi, M. F., Morthorst-Jensen, D. A. M., Christiansen, E., Rauste, P., Slaidins, I., & Vellemaa, T. (2022). D2.8: Open Science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries (final report). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6503709>

Objective: This activity will help participants analyse real-world Open Science policy examples, identify key stakeholders and topics, and evaluate challenges and opportunities for implementing Open Science practices through policy, fostering both individual reflection and group discussion skills.

Lecture 2: Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices: Impact

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Illustrate with examples the ways in which Open Science policies underpin Open Science practices.
- Interpret the rationale behind various Open Science policies and their intended outcomes.
- Analyse the interaction between Open Science policies and practices in various institutional and national contexts.

Lecture 3: Challenges of Implementing and Barriers to Open Science

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Analyse how traditional academic metrics of success might conflict with the principles of Open Science.
- Identify challenges associated with implementing Open Science.
- Describe how Open Science can be integrated into the research process.
- Propose strategies to overcome challenges in implementing Open Science.

Lecture 4: Cultural Changes require for Open Science Adoption

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Define research culture.
- Explain the connection between culture and Open Science.
- Identify cultural changes and evaluate strategies available to promote and encourage Open Science.

Activity: Barriers to Open Research

Objective: Open science is key to advancing research and innovation, but various barriers make its implementation challenging. In this activity, participants will explore these barriers and propose solutions to overcome them.

Lecture 5: Responsible Research Assessment Movement

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Get an overview of the origins of Responsible Research Assessment movement.
- Connect Open Science Practices with RRA Movement.
- Establish a connection between OS Policy-making with RRA Movement.

Lecture 6: Open Science Infrastructures

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Define Open Science Infrastructures (OSIs)
- Identify how Policy-makers can support OSIs

3.18 Module 18: Implementing Open Science Policies

Aims of the module: equip participants with the knowledge and practical tools needed to implement Open Science policies effectively, focusing on integrating Open Science workflows into research practices and organisational strategies.

Lecture 1: Open Science Workflows

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Identify challenges and key priorities in Open Science policy implementation.

Activity: Designing an Open Science Workflow

Objective: In this activity, participants explore the steps of the research workflow and consider how Open Science practices can be applied in different scenarios. This reflective exercise helps them think critically about the opportunities and challenges of adopting Open Science in their work.

3.19 Module 19: From developing to evaluating Open Science policies

Aims of the module: develop skills for designing Open Science policies in practice, focusing on key elements for policy development, implementation, and evaluation.

Lecture 1: Designing Open Science policies in practice

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- List the essential elements of Open Science policies.
- Explain how Open Science policies transform values and principles into practical requirements, mandates and recommendations.
- Explain how Open Science policies can be monitored and evaluated.

Activity: Evaluating Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in Open Science

Objective: This activity aims to enhance participants' ability to critically evaluate Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in the context of Open Science. By reflecting on their strengths, weaknesses, and practical relevance, they will better understand how KPIs can be applied effectively in real-world Open Science contexts, fostering a more nuanced understanding of their role and potential impact.

3.20 Module 20: Open Science Policies Adaptation

Aims of the module: explore how Open Science policies can be adapted to align with new evidence and evolving circumstances.

Lecture 1: Adapt policies based on new evidence and changing circumstances

Learning objectives:

By the end of this lecture, the participants will be able to:

- Adapt policies based on new evidence and changing circumstances.

Additional Reading: Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres. A description is provided in *section 7.1.2*.

Additional Reading: Advancing evidence-based policymaking through Open Collections and Open Science Principles. A description is provided in *section 7.1.3*.

Final Activity: Design your own Open Science Training Session

Objective: The aim of this activity is to put some of the newly acquired skills from this learning path into practice and to design an Open Science Training Session for a relevant community in the participant's country. This activity prepares participants for future activities as a master trainer in their country or region.

4 Training Implementation and Delivery, and Certification

4.1 Digital Tools and Content Formats

The training program was implemented through a blended learning approach, combining self-paced and live online sessions to provide flexibility while maintaining interactive elements. To support this delivery model, several tools and platforms were used both for developing the content and for engaging participants during the sessions.

The **Skills4EOsc Learning (Moodle) platform**¹³ served as the central learning environment, hosting all training materials, assignments, assessments, and announcements. Its structured layout enabled easy navigation through modules, while built-in features supported tracking of progress and interaction with the content.

BigBlueButton (BBB) was the primary tool used for delivering the live online sessions. It facilitated real-time interaction between trainers and participants, with features such as breakout rooms for group activities, enhancing engagement. BBB was integrated into the Moodle platform, allowing seamless access without additional logins or transitions.

To promote interaction and collect live information during synchronous sessions, both **Wooclap** and **Mentimeter** were used during the different phases of the training. These tools enabled trainers to run polls, quizzes, and open-ended questions in real time, fostering active participation. Additionally, they provided opportunities to gather more information about the audience's background, expectations, and understanding.

To create engaging and accessible materials, **AI-powered voiceover tools**, were employed to narrate video lectures. This ensured consistency in tone and pacing across videos, while also saving production time. These narrated lectures were further edited using video editing software to integrate visuals,

¹³ <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/>

animations, and transitions, improving clarity and maintaining participant attention. By prioritising **video lectures with voiceover** for the self-paced part of the course, a better learning experience was achieved. These lectures allowed participants to absorb the content at their own pace, with the added benefit of visual and auditory reinforcement. Accompanying the videos were **slide decks** in multiple formats (PowerPoint, OpenDocumentPresentation, and PDF) to ensure compatibility and ease of use. Additionally, **instructor notes** in Word and OpenDocumentText formats gave facilitators guidance for delivering the content, including talking points and suggestions.

This multimodal content delivery, supported by digital tools and platforms, ensured that the training was accessible, engaging, and adaptable across different learning styles and technical environments.

4.2 Assessment methods included in the courses

Assessment played a key role in the design and implementation of the EIDM learning path, serving not only as a tool for certification but also as an essential pedagogical element that would support the knowledge retention, self-evaluation and practical application. In a learning environment characterised by openness, flexibility and self-directed participation, the assessment strategy needed to cover multiple purposes. Besides validating the acquisition of certain competences, it was important to offer meaningful feedback and continuous engagement, while being accessible and manageable for adult professionals with different time constraints and levels of prior knowledge. Activities and assessments were therefore carefully integrated in the training courses to align with the learning objectives and structured in a way to allow participants to reflect on and apply the presented concepts. Whether used for formal certification or for personal progress tracking, they were designed to be relevant to the course concepts and real-world applications, covering the needs of adult learners, while keeping their interest throughout the learning experience.

In the first round of the TtT, the assessments included individual assignments linked to the self-paced content, along with quizzes. Some of them were used also as group activities during the live sessions, with their dual use serving

both collaborative discussions and self-reflection. While this approach supported deeper engagement, it required more time from participants during the self-paced part and manual grading by the trainers, making the training less scalable and self-sustaining.

To improve efficiency and better support busy professionals, in the second round, the individual assignments were replaced by “suggested activities for reuse” with clear guidelines, as well as structured quizzes for each lecture. These quizzes allowed participants to self-assess their understanding, offered automatic feedback and eliminated the need for manual evaluation. To maintain integrity and fairness, the quizzes were extended in length and scope, and limited to three attempts, while using randomised questions in each try. This approach promoted genuine comprehension, rather than rote repetition and memorisation, and ensured participants remained engaged with the content.

Types of activities/assessments

Below we present all the types of activities and assessments that were used in all rounds of training.

Self-paced Activities:

- **Quizzes:** In round 1, selected lectures included short quizzes focused on basic recall and understanding. In round 2, longer and more summative quizzes followed each lecture, incorporating randomised questions and limited attempts.
- **Individual Assignments:** In round 1, individual assignments were used both as self-paced assessments and the basis for live group discussions, supporting personal reflection and peer interaction. In round 2, they were no longer mandatory for the self-paced part, but offered as suggested resources for reuse in future trainings and/or activities to prepare for the live session, since some of them were used again as group activities during live sessions.

Live Session Activities (both round 1 and 2):

- **Group Activities:** Group activities encouraged collaboration and practical application of the learning concepts, through case studies, roleplay, scenario analyses, and group discussions during the live sessions. This approach supported community building and peer learning, helping participants to deepen their understanding and reflect on real-world challenges and contexts, through meaningful discussions.
- **Discussions:** Discussions in between the different activities and presentations allowed participants to better understand the learning concepts, clarify open issues and engage to interactive dialogues, enriching the learning experience and sharing personal ideas and views.
- **Demo Activities:** Demo activities were used only for the purposes of some Live sessions. During the demo activities, some tools were presented that served as additional learning material to complement the core content, engaging participants to search more advanced concepts and resources.

All the above activities, contributed to the participants' overall learning experience, with quizzes and assignments playing a direct role in the certification process, by assessing the knowledge and skills required for the courses completion.

4.3 Certification process

As mentioned before, the Skills4EOSC project operates a dedicated e-learning platform¹⁴, built on Moodle and managed by GARR. This platform serves as the central hub for Open Science training, instructor accreditation, and certification through a comprehensive Recognition Framework¹⁵ that implements a sophisticated micro-credentialing system using digital badges as the primary mechanism for recognising and validating Open Science competences.

¹⁴ Link to the Skills4EOSC learning platform: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu>

¹⁵ Weisteen Bjerde, K., Green, D., Bjønnes, L., van Leersum, N., Filiposka, S., Kjørveziroski, V., Janik, J., Hadrossek, C., Bernier, M., Sowinski, C., Torres-Ramos, G., Antoine, D., Mendez Rodriguez, E. M., Lavitrano, M., Whyte, A., Di Giorgio, S., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.4 Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework first iteration. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14797078>

Individual micro-credentials are awarded upon successful demonstration of specific competences within courses and learning paths. For example, participants completing courses within the EIDM learning path, a series of 7 courses, receive separate badges for each course. Complete instructor accreditation is achieved when participants successfully earn all required micro-credentials within a specific learning path, with the final certification badge representing the culmination of multiple demonstrated competences. This process requires evidence-based assessment, where learners must demonstrate practical application of skills through completion of self-paced modules, participation in live sessions, and various submissions.

The platform has been enhanced with open digital badges support, developed in coordination with the Skills4EOSC FAIR-by-design Methodology and Task 2.5 recommendations. Since Moodle (version 3.8 and above) is certified as an Open Badges v2.0 issuer, all badges follow the latest Open Badges standards, ensuring they can be read and seamlessly imported into badge backpacks. To facilitate easy collection and sharing of credentials beyond the Skills4EOSC project, the learning platform connects with the Badge backpack¹⁶, one of the most popular badge storage solutions. This integration enables users to organise, manage, and publicly display their digital credentials obtained during various training activities, providing verifiable proof of their Open Science competences and successful completion of training components.

Further details on the accreditation and certification process are available in the final version of the Recognition Framework¹⁷.

In the below table you can find all the badges that were created for the EIDM learning path, including their icon and description for each badge/course.

¹⁶ <https://badgr.com/>

¹⁷ Bjerde, K. W., Green, D., Bjønnes, L., van Leersum, N., Filiposka, S., Kjørveziroski, V., Janik, J., Hadrossek, C., Bernier, M., Sowinski, C., Torres Ramos, G., Antoine, D., Forni, M., Rinaldi, L., & Corleto, A. (2025). D2.8 Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework - Final version. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14933037>

Table 3: Description of Certification Badges created for the EIDM Learning Path

Badge Icon	Badge Name	Description
	Fundamentals on Open Science Specialist	The "Fundamentals on Open Science Specialist" badge is awarded for completing the first course in the "Open Science and Evidence Informed Decision Making" learning path. It represents the participant's foundational understanding of Open Science, including its core values and practices, and their readiness to promote transparency and collaboration in the research process.
	Introduction to ELSI and Data Governance Specialist	The "Introduction to ELSI and Data Governance Specialist" badge is awarded for completing the second course in the "Open Science and Evidence Informed Decision Making" learning path. This badge recognises the participant's understanding of the Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) of Open Science and the principles of data governance.
	Introduction to Evidence-Informed Decision Making Specialist	The "Introduction to Evidence-Informed Decision Making Specialist" badge is awarded for completing the third course in the "Open Science and Evidence Informed Decision Making" learning path. This badge reflects the participant's understanding of how evidence informs decisions, the roles of various stakeholders, and the practical tools used in data-driven decision-making.
	Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies Specialist	The "Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies Specialist" badge is awarded for completing the fourth course in the "Open Science and Evidence Informed Decision Making" learning path. This badge reflects an understanding of stakeholder roles in Open Science, effective collaboration strategies, and the practical approaches for fostering inclusive and

		transparent scientific practices.
	Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science Specialist	The "Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science Specialist" badge is awarded for completing the fifth course in the "Open Science and Evidence Informed Decision Making" learning path. This badge represents the participant's understanding of the essential roles of funding, capacity building, and institutional support in promoting Open Science practices, as well as the use of AI in Open Science and evidence-informed decision making.
	Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices Specialist	The "Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices Specialist" badge is awarded for completing the sixth course in the "Open Science and Evidence Informed Decision Making" learning path. This badge demonstrates knowledge of the development and implementation of Open Science policies, the challenges and barriers to their adoption, the cultural shifts required to foster openness in research, and the responsible research assessment movement.
	Implementing Open Science Policies Specialist	The "Implementing Open Science Policies Specialist" badge is awarded for completing the seventh and final course in the "Open Science and Evidence Informed Decision Making" learning path. This badge demonstrates knowledge on Open Science Workflows, development and evaluation of Open Science policies, as well as adaptation of Open Science Policies based on new evidence and circumstances.
	Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making Instructor	This badge is awarded to the Master Trainers, who have successfully completed all seven courses in the "Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making" learning path. It certifies their expertise in topics related to Open Science

		<p>fundamentals, ELSI and data governance, evidence-informed decision making, collaboration and communication strategies with stakeholders, investing, capacity building and AI in Open Science, as well as Open Science Policies Practices and Implementation.</p>
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The image below illustrates the badge hierarchy for the “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” (EIDM) learning path. Each of the seven individual courses awards a badge upon successful completion. Participants who complete all seven courses receive an additional instructor badge, recognising full completion of the learning path.

4.4 Training Delivery Phases

The training program was delivered in three distinct phases: a pilot phase followed by two rounds of final training sessions. Each phase had its own importance and contributed to refining the training content and delivery.

Pilot Phase: The pilot phase (M19-M22) provided an initial test of the training materials with a smaller group of participants, coming only from the Skills4EOSC Consortium. During this phase, all lectures were delivered

synchronously, and the focus was mainly on content delivery rather than extensive live activities. While there were a few group activities and some sessions using Mentimeter for live feedback, the pilot phase lacked the robust interaction that would later become a key feature of the program. The aim was to test the foundational content and structure of the training. Based on the feedback, it became clear that adding a more balanced combination of synchronous and asynchronous learning would benefit future phases, offering participants the flexibility to engage with content at their own pace, while maintaining interactivity through shorter live sessions.

Table 4: Content details and Schedule of Pilot TtT trainings

No. of course	Course Outline - Topics	Date
Pilot 1: "Open Science is the new Norm"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamentals of Open Science • Open Science vs. Closed Science • Accountability and Transparency in Open Science • Open Science and Society • Legal and Ethical Frameworks and Considerations in Open Science • Data Governance and Legislative Strategies for FAIR Research 	Thursday, June 20, 2024, 09:00 - 13:30 CEST
Pilot 2: "Open Science Stakeholders and Evidence-informed Decision Making"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding Open Science and Its Stakeholders • Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders • Capacity Building and Training Programs in Open Science • Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision Making • Evidence-informed Decision Making - outputs and tools 	Monday, June 17, 2024, 09:00 - 13:15 CEST
Pilot 3: "Policy Making in Open Science"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy making in Open Science • Open science policies support Open Science practices • Role of Policy Makers in Supporting Open Science Practices • Implementing Open Science policies • Monitoring and Evaluation of Open Science Policies 	Wednesday, June 26, 2024, 09:00 - 16:00 CEST

Figure 3: The cover page of the Learning Path

Round 1: Building on the lessons learned from the pilot phase, Round 1 introduced a blended delivery model with both synchronous (live sessions) and asynchronous (self-paced materials) components. This shift allowed participants to engage with content at their own pace and actively participate during live sessions. Round 1 included more interactive elements than the pilot phase, such as individual assignments, group activities, Q&A sessions, and live polls, which significantly improved engagement. Feedback collected during Round 1 highlighted areas for further refinement and served as the foundation for adjustments made in Round 2.

Round 2: Round 2 was launched in response to the high demand for the training after Round 1, where limited seats were initially offered to ensure better engagement with a manageable group size. With a larger participant base in Round 2, the structure from Round 1 was mainly retained, but with some adjustments to manage the larger groups while maintaining engagement. Importantly, Round 2 also included updates to the training materials based on the feedback from Round 1. These updates involved refining the content and adjusting the structure of some modules and group activities during the live sessions. Both Round 1 and Round 2 provided the certification described above.

Table 5: Content Details per Course and Schedule of live sessions in both rounds

No. of course	Course Outline - Topics	R1 Live session	R2 Live session
EIDM Training Course 1: "Open Science is the new Norm"¹⁸	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module 01: Fundamentals of Open Science Module 02: Open Science and Society Module 03: Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation Module 04: Open Science vs. Closed Science Module 05: Accountability and Transparency in Open Science 	Friday,18/10/24 10.00-12.00CET	Friday,04/04/25 10.00-12:00CET
EIDM Training Course 2: "Ethical Legal and Societal Implications (ELSI) and Data Governance"¹⁹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module 06: Legal and Ethical Frameworks and Considerations in Open Science Module 07: Open Science under the EU Data Regulatory Framework Module 08: Data Governance and Legislative Strategies for FAIR Research 	Friday,25/10/24 10.00-12.00CET	Monday,14/04/25 10.00 -12:00CET
EIDM Training Course 3: "Introduction to Evidence-Informed Decision Making"²⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module 09: Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision Making Module 10: Evidence-informed decision making - outputs and tools 	Friday,08/11/24 10.00-12.00CET	Thursday,24/04/25 10.00-12:00CET
EIDM Training Course 4: "Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies"²¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module 11: Open Science and its Stakeholders Module 12: Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders 	Friday,15/11/24 10.00-12.00CET	Monday,12/05/25 10.00-12:00CET
EIDM Training Course 5: "Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science"²²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module 13: Investing in Open Science Module 14: Capacity Building and Training Programs in Open Science Module 15: Open Science and Artificial Intelligence 	Friday,22/11/24 14.00-16.00CET	Friday,23/05/25 10.00-12:00CET
EIDM Training Course 6: "Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices"²³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module 16: Open Science Policies Module 17: Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices 	Friday,29/11/24 13.00-15.00CET	Tuesday,03/06/25 10.00-12:00CET

¹⁸The final material is available as a self-paced course in the Skills4EOSC platform: <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/course/view.php?id=82>, as well as in Zenodo in the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948365>

¹⁹ The final material is available as a self-paced course in the Skills4EOSC platform: <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/course/view.php?id=83>, as well as in Zenodo in the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948377>

²⁰ The final material is available as a self-paced course in the Skills4EOSC platform: <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/course/view.php?id=84>, as well as in Zenodo in the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948390>

²¹ The final material is available as a self-paced course in the Skills4EOSC platform: <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/course/view.php?id=85>, as well as in Zenodo in the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948394>

²² The final material is available as a self-paced course in the Skills4EOSC platform: <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/course/view.php?id=86>, as well as in Zenodo in the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948396>

²³ The final material is available as a self-paced course in the Skills4EOSC platform:

EIDM Training Course 7: "Implementing Open Science Policies"²⁴	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 18: Implementing Open Science Policies • Module 19: From developing to evaluating Open Science policies • Module 20: Open Science Policies Adaptation 	Friday,06/12/24 13.00-15.00CET	Monday,13/06/25 10.00-12:00CET
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Self-paced-only Courses: Following the conclusion of the two rounds of training, which included live sessions as mentioned above, all courses were transformed into fully self-paced formats, hosted in the Skills4EOSC learning platform. This transition was made to broaden access and provide greater flexibility, allowing individuals to engage with the material at their own convenience, even after the end of the project. Participants can now freely self-enroll and navigate the courses independently, progressing through the modules at a pace that suits their personal and professional commitments.

While the self-paced courses maintain the core content and learning objectives established during the live training rounds, they differ in the certification approach. Instead of offering a formal accreditation with digital badges as we did in the previous two main rounds, this version provides only certification of attendance upon successful completion (keeping in mind that the project will have ended). The self-assessment activities that are included serve only for self-evaluation of the knowledge acquired in each module. This shift to self-paced learning reflects an emphasis on lifelong learning and accessibility, enabling continuous professional development in the field.

<https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=87>, as well as in Zenodo in the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948404>

²⁴ The final material is available as a self-paced course in the Skills4EOSC platform: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=88>, as well as in Zenodo in the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948408>

5 Participation and Engagement

The “Open Science and Evidence-informed Decision-Making” (EIDM) learning path reflected the broad international engagement and multi-national identity of the Skills4EOSC project. Over the course of two rounds, with seven thematic courses each, the training can report significant numbers on participation and reach:

A quick summary:

- Total number of courses: 7 per round
- Total number of enrolments: 805
- Unique number of participants: 180
- Unique countries represented: 27
- Unique organisations involved: 102
- Total material views across all courses in Round 2²⁵: 30,903

These figures reflect both the growing relevance of Open Science and the effectiveness of the training model in engaging different stakeholders, such as researchers, data stewards, policy professionals, infrastructure experts, etc. from around the world. While policymakers, civil servants, knowledge brokers and in general decision makers are the final target audience of the learning path, we consider a strength the fact that participation came from a diverse type of stakeholders interested in becoming trainers of such a target a group.

Below we present an overview of participation and completion rates for each of the seven courses within the EIDM learning path. The table includes the number of participants²⁶ that enrolled in each course and the number of participants who successfully completed all the requirements of each course and were awarded a badge as of the date of this report. It is important to

²⁵ Due to a limitation with the platform, we could only retrieve accurate numbers for Round 2. We opted to share them to show the size of engagement with the materials and activities.

²⁶ In the first round a lot of project/WP3 participants were included in the registered users either participating as trainers or just having access to the final material for further reuse, but they are not included in the final numbers.

note, that the course received interest in both rounds, which indicates its usefulness and relevance for Open Science actors.

Table 6: Total number of participation per course across both rounds. Including number of badges awarded.

Course Title	Participants Enrolled	Badges Awarded
<i>Training course 1: "Open Science is the new norm"</i>	Round 1: 51	Round 1: 18
	Round 2: 53	Round 2: 33
<i>Training course 2: "Introduction to ELSI and Data Governance"</i>	Round 1: 50	Round 1: 22
	Round 2: 57	Round 2: 35
<i>Training course 3: "Introduction to Evidence-Informed Decision Making"</i>	Round 1: 50	Round 1: 18
	Round 2: 61	Round 2: 33
<i>Training course 4: "Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies"</i>	Round 1: 49	Round 1: 19
	Round 2: 67	Round 2: 27
<i>Training course 5: "Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science"</i>	Round 1: 50	Round 1: 20
	Round 2: 66	Round 2: 27
<i>Training course 6: "Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices"</i>	Round 1: 52	Round 1: 20
	Round 2: 71	Round 2: 27
<i>Training course 7: "Implementing Open Science Policies"</i>	Round 1: 52	Round 1: 22
	Round 2: 76	Round 2: 28
<i>Final Instructors Badge (participants that completed successfully all 7 courses in the Learning Path)</i>		Round 1: 14 Round 2: 24

The difference between enrolment and completion rates reflects the flexible and open nature of the training. Participation in the course was entirely voluntary, and access was granted to anyone interested in the topic, regardless of their availability to complete all activities, even if the estimated time needed to complete the course was clearly stated in the course description. It was obvious that some participants joined primarily to explore the materials, while others underestimated the time they could commit once the course began. This highlights the common challenge in online and

blended environments, especially among busy professionals. It is important to note that registration in the last 2 courses for round 2 exceeded 80 registrations and for that reason we stopped receiving applications to ensure a manageable number of participants and engaging environment during the live sessions.

Overview of Round 1

Participation by Country:

Participation in Round 1 of the EIDM learning path reflects the broad engagement with Open Science across Europe. The course gathered participants from 21 countries, illustrating the geographical diversity of interest. While the countries represented largely align with the communication channels and networks established within the project, the extent of participation remains a positive indication of the project’s reach and relevance.

Table 7: Top 10 Countries by Attendance for Round 1, across all 7 courses.

Italy emerged as the most prominent country in terms of attendance, with a total of 56 course attendances across the training series. France followed

with 35 attendances, and Greece with 28, highlighting their active engagement with the project. Countries such as Bulgaria, Norway, Tunisia, and the United Kingdom also showed significant participation, each with 21 attendances. Meanwhile, Estonia, Germany, North Macedonia, Poland, Slovakia, Spain, and Sweden each registered 14 attendances, signalling a solid level of institutional and individual interest across both established and developing research environments.

Participation by Organisations:

The majority of participants were affiliated with universities, highlighting the central role of higher education in leading Open Science transitions. These were complemented by a strong presence of participants from national research infrastructures such as CSC in Finland, GRNET in Greece, CNR in Italy and SIKT in Norway. These infrastructures play a critical role in developing and delivering Open Science services, data stewardship and national coordination.

Several participants also came from academies of sciences, government agencies, and scientific libraries or information centres, such as the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information and the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, indicating the variety of institutions needed to support the adoption of Open Science on a systemic level. The inclusion of professionals from cultural institutions and museums also reflects the relevance of Open Science principles to heritage and knowledge-sharing domains.

Overview of Round 2

Participation by Country:

Across the seven EIDM training courses in round 2, participation spanned 22 countries, reflecting a truly international and interdisciplinary effort to advance Open Science practices. Italy had again the highest overall representation, with 189 attendances recorded across all courses. Following Italy, Spain and Poland emerged as key contributors, with 50 and 48 attendances respectively. Their consistent presence across courses signals a growing institutional commitment to Open Science, both at the policy and implementation levels. France (40 attendances), Greece (32), and Austria (24)

also demonstrated robust engagement. Other countries such as Sweden (22), Norway (18), and Chile (13) showed meaningful involvement, indicating that Open Science awareness is taking hold across diverse research ecosystems.

Table 8: Top 10 Countries by Attendance in Round 2, across all 7 courses.

Smaller but notable attendance was observed from countries such as Finland, Germany, Brazil, Mexico, North Macedonia, Luxembourg, Uruguay, Switzerland, Russia, the UK, Venezuela, the Netherlands, and Bulgaria. The inclusion of these countries underscores a conscious effort to include both well-established and emerging research environments. Finally, despite relatively small numbers, the presence of participants from beyond the EU highlights the expanding reach of Skills4EOSC across regions.

Altogether, the data reveals a vibrant and expanding community of stakeholders engaged in the transformation of Open Science, while also offering valuable insights into how the learning path resonates across different national and cultural contexts. While countries like Italy lead in terms of volume, the broad geographic spread of participation points to a shared commitment to openness, collaboration, and responsible research across borders and disciplines.

Participation by Organisations:

The total number of unique organisations across all courses is 102. Several organisations have a strong presence across multiple courses, indicating their consistent involvement.

- The Università degli Studi di Milano is the most frequent participant, appearing 18 times.
- The University of Turin and Universidad Carlos III de Madrid also show significant engagement, appearing 16 and 14 times, respectively.
- Other highly active organizations include University of Bologna and Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, each appearing 10 times.

The list of unique organisations participating across all seven courses reflects a rich and diverse spectrum of institutions engaged in Open Science and evidence-informed decision-making. There is a strong presence of research-performing universities from Europe and even from Latin America (e.g., University of Bologna, University of Warsaw, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Universidade Federal do Ceará), indicating sustained academic interest in embedding Open Science practices. National research institutes and public research bodies (e.g., CNR in Italy, CEA in France) are well represented, signalling institutional commitment to infrastructure, policy, and capacity-building. Several libraries, data services, and digital infrastructure organisations (e.g., Luxembourg National Data Service, Swedish National Data Service, Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire) underscore the centrality of RDM and FAIR principles. The inclusion of museums, health research foundations, and hybrid/independent organisations broadens the ecosystem beyond universities, showing cross-sectoral relevance. Finally, participation from countries such as Chile, Mexico, Brazil, and Uruguay highlight the programme's international reach and inclusivity beyond the EU.

Engagement with materials: total views

Across the seven Open Science training courses in Round 2, a total of 30,903 views was recorded.

Table 9: Total views per course for Round 2 only. Views include interaction with any of the materials released under each course e.g. Presentations, transcripts, videos, quizzes, assignments or forums.

The viewership data for the seven courses in the Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision-Making training series shows a clear downward trend in total views across the course sequence. These fluctuations are primarily explained by the timing of course releases. The earlier courses have simply had more time online, allowing them to accumulate a greater number of views. Also, across all courses the majority of views were gathered either the week the material was released online (preparation phase for live session), or the week of the live session, showcasing the impact of the live sessions in driving interaction with the materials.

Table 10: Course release timeline from March to June 2025. Earlier courses had more time to accumulate views, explaining part of the variation in engagement across the series.

SCIENCE4POLICY	OPEN SCIENCE IS THE NEW NORM	Async + Sync	From 26/03 to 4/04
	ELSI AND DATA GOVERNANCE	Async + Sync	From 5/04 to 14/04
	INTRODUCTION TO EVIDENCE-INFORMED DECISION-MAKING	Async + Sync	From 15/04 to 25/04
	OPEN SCIENCE STAKEHOLDERS AND COLLABORATION STRATEGIES	Async + Sync	From 3/05 to 12/05
	EMPOWERING THE FUTURE OF RESEARCH WITH OPEN SCIENCE	Async + Sync	From 13/05 to 23/05
	OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES SUPPORT OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES	Async + Sync	From 24/05 to 2/06
	IMPLEMENTING OPEN SCIENCE POLICIES	Async + Sync	From 3/06 to 13/06

This does not necessarily reflect a decline in interest or quality, but rather the natural progression of cumulative view counts over time. Additionally, the high viewership of Courses 1 and 2 may reflect their foundational nature, drawing in a broader audience seeking introductory content on Open Science principles and data governance. It's also worth noting that Course 6 shows a slight uptick in views (3,433) compared to Course 5 (2,382), suggesting a renewed interest in policy-related themes, possibly tied to outreach efforts or the relevance of the topic at the time of release. Courses 6 and 7 also showed higher registration count, and that could potentially explain the uptick in views.

Overall, the data shows that the project utilised its network effectively to gather a lot of interest and participation in these courses. Policy making remains a key enabler for Open Science to become a reality and the future reusability of those resources alongside the trainers that it produced can greatly support potential discussions to implement changes.

6 Feedback, Evaluation and Impact

6.1 Feedback Collection Process

To evaluate the effectiveness and relevance of the “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” (EIDM) Learning Path, participant feedback was collected after each of the seven courses and at the end of the learning path. Evaluation forms captured both quantitative and qualitative responses on various aspects, including content clarity, relevance, usability, engagement and overall satisfaction. You can find the Evaluation Form that was used at the end of each course and the one used at the end of the learning path in Annex A, at the end of this document.

6.1.1 Methodology Summary

The evaluation forms were included in the learning platform, as a final activity of each course. Each participant was asked to complete one questionnaire after each course and for those attending the last (seventh) course of the EIDM learning path, the questionnaire was extended with some additional questions, in order to include information about the entire series of courses. The questions were all anonymous and no questions were mandatory, to give participants a choice of which questions to answer and to encourage honesty. Finally, it was up to the participant to include their contact details if they were willing to be contacted for additional feedback.

The total number of responses per course and round of trainings are provided in the table below.

Table 11: Number of Responses received by participants per round

<i>Course Title</i>	<i>Responses Received</i>
<i>Training course 1: “Open Science is the new norm”</i>	Round 1: 26 Round 2: 35
<i>Training course 2: “Introduction to ELSI and Data Governance”</i>	Round 1: 23 Round 2: 35
<i>Training course 3: “Introduction to Evidence-Informed Decision Making”</i>	Round 1: 22 Round 2: 34

Training course 4: "Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies"

Round 1: 20 Round 2: 28

Training course 5: "Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science"

Round 1: 20 Round 2: 27

Training course 6: "Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices"

Round 1: 20 Round 2: 28

Training course 7: "Implementing Open Science Policies" and Overall evaluation of the Learning Path

Round 1: 22 Round 2: 28

6.2 Participant Feedback Analysis

This section summarises the key findings from the participants' feedback and how they were used to improve the training.

6.2.1 Key Findings

We start the analysis with some qualitative data, extracted from the evaluation. These include:

Self-paced structure and format diversity: Participants expressed strong appreciation for the self-paced structure, which allowed them to engage with the content at their own pace, despite time constraints. The use of varied formats, such as videos, documents, readings, presentations, activities, was highly valued for enhancing engagement and supporting diverse learning preferences. Notably, the instructors' notes with the narrative of the lectures were frequently mentioned as especially helpful. They contributed to a deeper and easier understanding of the content, particularly for participants whose first language is not English. In addition, these notes were mentioned to be a very useful reference for those intending to reuse the material in their own training activities.

Time consumed to complete the self-paced part of the course: Although participants greatly valued the flexibility of the self-paced format, many noted in certain courses that the time required to complete the material was greater than initially estimated. As the self-paced period was limited to a single week for round 1 and ten days for round 2, this made the course feel intense in workload, especially for those balancing training with ongoing professional responsibilities.

Assessment workload: In the first round, some participants noted that the individual assignments, whilst really valuable for engagement and reflection, added to the overall workload alongside the rest of the course material and their professional responsibilities. Additionally, in the same round, several learners mentioned that some quizzes were relatively easy, suggesting the need to advance assessment difficulty.

Live session interactivity and duration: Some participants in the first round expressed the need for more dedicated time to group activities during the live session, as the recaps and presentations shortened the opportunities for discussion. Although the second round allocated more time for group activities and discussion, there were participants that requested longer sessions overall to allow for even more interaction and exchange.

Content value and relevance of topics: The training content was highly valued as an effective beginners' course, providing a comprehensive overview of topics related to diverse aspects of Open Science and decision making. While some participants noted that certain subjects could benefit from deeper exploration, such as ELSI and AI, this was aligned with the course's intentional design to raise a broad awareness in all of the necessary aspects and focus more on the topics related to decision making.

Emphasis of practical examples: Participants also highlighted the value of practical examples. While many appreciated the existing practical examples, there were some participants that requested for additional, diverse examples to further enhance understanding, especially for more complex topics like ELSI.

Below you can also find the results of the quantitative analysis of the feedback, in terms of total experience, gained knowledge, satisfaction, structure and content and confidence in applying the gain knowledge in a professional context.

Reflections on the user experience for each course: To better understand the participants' overall impressions of each course, they were asked to rate several aspects of their experience, including content relevance, clarity of information presented, pacing of the course, usefulness of the activities,

effectiveness of the instructors and the learning environment. Using a rating scale from 1 to 5 (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree), we received the following results per round:

Round 1: Round 1 feedback indicates a consistently positive experience, particularly in content relevance and quality of instruction. Minor concerns around pacing and usefulness of activities are mentioned. In more detail:

- The strongest-rated area overall, with an average score of 4.34, is related to content relevance, which shows that the course topics resonated with the participants’ expectations and professional needs.
- Content clarity and effectiveness scored more than 4.2, which reflects solid delivery and instructional quality across the different courses.
- The learning environment was also well rated, with an average score of 4.27, suggesting that the format, tools and overall atmosphere supported learning effectively.
- Finally, pacing scored an average of 3.97 across courses, which shows that some learners found the course a bit intense, as is also depicted in the qualitative analysis.
- Overall, all courses scored consistently above 4 in most categories, giving a very important result on satisfaction, but of course with room for improvement.

The analysis in each category per course is also depicted in the diagram below.

Round 2: Round 2 feedback confirms the continued participant satisfaction and some points for improvement in certain aspects of the learning experience. The results reflect a consistently strong performance across all categories, with slightly increased scores in pacing and learning environment, compared with round 1. In more detail:

- Content relevance remained one of the most highly rated aspects, with an average score of 4.33, reaffirming that the material met participants’ professional expectations and interests, in this group of people as well.
- Content clarity and instructors effectiveness again scored above 4.2, showing the well-received delivery and teaching consistency across courses.
- The learning environment showed a small improvement from the previous round, averaging 4.27, again highlighting a well-organised and engaging learning experience.
- Pacing also improved with an average of 4.00, suggesting that the adjusted course duration and streamlined workload better matched learners needs.
- Although the usefulness of activities was the lowest rated aspect, at 4.03, it reflects high satisfaction, while indicating an area to further improve in future settings.
- Overall, round 2 maintained the high levels of satisfaction in the audience across all elements, with early adjustments from round 1 contributing positively to the learners experience.

This analysis of round 2 is also provided in the diagram below.

Courses recommendation: Another factor to assess the course overall satisfaction came through the question whether participants would recommend the course to a colleague. Participants could choose from three options: Yes (would recommend), Possibly (might recommend), or No (would not recommend). The following results present the status of each round.

Round 1: Across all courses in round 1, the large majority of participants responded “Yes”, with individual courses receiving between 13 to 21 positive endorsements, depending on the participation in each course survey, all adding up to more than 75% of

the participants. A smaller number selected “Possibly”, about 2-4 per course (8-20%) and very few said “No” (only 1 in course 3 and 7, with less than 5%). This suggests a strong overall satisfaction and willingness to recommend the courses to a wider audience.

Round 2: In round 2, the trend continues positively, with an increase in the total responses per course and an additional increase in “Yes” responses for most of the courses, particularly Course 1 (97%). “Possibly” responses increased slightly in

some courses (with a span between 3-20%), but “No” remained very low (0-2 per course, with less than 6%). This round shows even stronger endorsement, while again indicating some possible improvements.

Level of knowledge prior to the course and knowledge enhancement:

Level of knowledge prior to the course on the topics addressed by each course (in a scale 1-3, with 1: Novice, 2: Intermediate, 3: Expert) and

knowledge enhancement through the participation to each course (in a scale 1-3, 1: Not really, 2: Somewhat, 3: Considerably) were two other factors that were really interesting to measure.

Participants across both rounds entered the course series, in general, with **novice to intermediate prior knowledge** on most Open Science topics, which shows that the course targeted the expected audience as a beginners course. Average self-assessed prior knowledge scores ranged mostly between 1.4 and 2.2, showing a solid foundation in more familiar topics such as Open Science and FAIR principle, while more technical or policy-specific topics (e.g Cultural Change, Responsible Research Assessment, AI in Open Science, etc) tended to have a lower baseline familiarity.

Despite varying levels of starting expertise, **participants consistently reported a moderate to considerable enhancement** in their understanding across all topics. This was especially notable in areas where prior knowledge was low, such as Citizen Science, Legal Frameworks, Communication of Uncertainty, and Stakeholders Collaboration. This highlights the effectiveness of course in existing knowledge gaps and learners experience.

Round 2 participants showed in general lower prior knowledge on average than round 1 participants, especially in more advance topics, such as Ethical Issues, Open Science Workflows and Research Integrity. However, they also reported consistently strong enhancement scores. This pattern reinforces the effectiveness of the course structure in onboarding participants with little prior exposure in certain topics.

Overall, this indicator suggests that the course series is well aligned with the needs of the target audience, effectively introducing core Open Science concepts while also deepening the participants' understanding in less familiar or emerging areas. These scores demonstrate that participants, not only felt more informed by the end of the courses, but also better equipped to engage with complex issues in Open Science, covering a wide range of topics related to policies, communication and implementation.

Overall satisfaction for the course series: Participants were also asked to rate their overall satisfaction with the course series (in a rating scale 1-5, 1: Very dissatisfied to 5: Very Satisfied), providing an indication of how well the training programme met their expectations and learning needs. In more detail:

Round 1: The majority of participants in round 1 reported a positive experience with the course series, with:

- 95% of respondents (19 out of 20 participants) indicating they were either “Satisfied” or “Very satisfied”.
- 5% of respondents (1 participant) reported dissatisfaction (“Dissatisfied”), while no one selected “Very dissatisfied” or “Neutral”.

These results reflect a strong initial reception of the course structure and content in round 1, while also highlighting a few areas for potential improvement, some of which were addressed in round 2. These statistics are depicted also in the diagram on the right.

Round 2: Feedback from participants in round 2 reflects a very high level of satisfaction with the course series:

- 68% (15 participants) were “Very satisfied”
- 27% (6 participants) were “Satisfied”
- 5% (1 participant) reported a “Neutral” experience
- 0% expressed dissatisfaction (either “Dissatisfied” or “Very dissatisfied”)

As depicted also in the diagram, overall 95% of respondents had a positive experience, which indicates that the improvements made after round 1 had a clear and positive impact on participant satisfaction.

Structure and Content of the course series: When participants were asked to evaluate the overall structure and content of the course series, we received the following responses per round.

Round 1: In round 1 the feedback shows that the majority of participants were very satisfied with the structure and content of the learning path. More specifically:

- 95% (19 out of 20) of participants found the structure to be at least good, with half of them rating it as excellent.
- Only one participant found the structure difficult to follow, which may indicate different individual learning styles or expectations.
- The results suggest the structure and content are overall well-designed and clear, but there is still minor room for optimisation.

Round 2: The feedback from round 2 shows a further improvement in participants' perception of the structure and content of the course.

- 100% (22 out of 22) of participants rated the structure and content of the course as either excellent or good. This indicated a strong positive response and reflects improvements made after round 1.
- 64% of participants rated the course excellent, suggesting that the structure was not only functional but also very well received. The complete absence of “Fair” or “Poor” responses underscores a successful refinement of the course’s structure and clarity, while some room for improvement still exist.

Confidence in applying gained knowledge in professional context: When asked about their confidence in applying the knowledge gained through the training to their professional context (in a rating scale 1-5, 1: Not Confident at all to 5: Very Confident), we received the following responses which highlight the perceived relevance and practical utility of the course content.

Round 1: Participants in round 1 overwhelmingly reported being confident about applying the knowledge gained through the courses to their professional context. More specifically:

- 85% (17 out of 20) of participants expressed confidence in applying the course content in their work, with 15% (3 out of 20) indicating they were either neutral or not very confident. No participants selected the lowest level of confidence.

- These results suggest the course successfully supported participants in building practical knowledge, though a small number of participants may benefit from additional support, related material, or more examples in different disciplines, to enhance confidence in real-world application.

Round 2: In round 2, the majority of participants felt confident in their ability to apply the knowledge from the course in a professional setting. In more detail:

- 76% (16 out of 21) of participants expressed confidence in applying the course content, while 24% (5 out of 21) remained neutral. Notably, no participants expressed a lack of confidence.
- The number of more "Neutral" responses in round 2 may indicate a broader range of participants with differing professional backgrounds or varying familiarity with the topics, while also provided insights to further reinforce practical examples or more contextual application exercises in future trainings.

We have also gathered some **highlights and testimonials** from the course participants, which you can find in **Annex B**, at the end of this document.

6.2.2 Use of Feedback for Improvement

The overall feedback during the two rounds of training was overwhelmingly positive. However, the key findings from the first round played a critical role in guiding important updates and refinements implemented in the second round. More specifically, these included:

Enhancing the self-paced learning experience and streamlining assessment format: In response to round 1 feedback regarding limited time and workload intensity, the self-paced learning period in round 2 was extended from one week to 10 days. This extension was carefully balanced, as further prolonging the timeframe risked participants losing momentum and forgetting material, which would negatively impact their engagement during the live sessions at the end of the self-paced part.

To further reduce workload and enhance the learning experience, individual assignments used in round 1 were removed in round 2. Instead they were offered as suggested activities for reuse and also meant to support preparation for the live session, where they were used as group activities. The only mandatory assessment method in round 2 became the quizzes, which were refined to serve a more meaningful role. Each lecture included a quiz composed of more nuanced and reflective questions. These were different for each attempt, with only three attempts allowed per participant, as they were randomly selected from a bank of questions. This approach was very positively received, as it encouraged deeper engagement and allowed learners to reflect more effectively on the acquired knowledge in each module.

Increasing interactivity during the live sessions: To address the feedback received in round 1, the live sessions in round 2 were refined to give greater emphasis on interactive elements, including group activities and discussions. At the same time, shorter recap sessions were retained, as participants in round 1 had found them helpful for reinforcing key messages. Nevertheless, in the feedback received in round 2, there were some suggestions to extend the live sessions to 3 hours, instead of 2 as in the initial setup, providing even more time for discussion for complex or high-interest topics. A further

extension of the live session could be foreseen in future activities, depending on audience needs and topic depth.

Expanding Practical Examples: Following the feedback for more practical examples, especially in complex areas, such as ELSI, round 2 materials were revised to include additional scenarios and case studies, including also examples from beyond the EU context. While it is not possible to cover every topic with exhaustive examples, they continue to be one of the most requested elements across different topics and disciplines, as they support better understanding and help connect theory to real-world application.

Maintaining Content Quality and Accessibility: The high-quality and accessibility of the training content were widely appreciated in both training rounds. To ensure consistency, round 2 retained the diverse format of material, while introducing additional document formats to further enhance accessibility and user-friendliness across devices and user needs. Moreover, additional readings were included in round 2, featuring material developed under other work package tasks and references to relevant resources. This helped enrich the overall content and provided opportunities for deeper engagement with key concepts, something that was really appreciated by the participants of round 2.

7 Relevant Additional Material and Events

As part of the training development under this WP, a significant effort was made to incorporate supplementary resources and outputs produced in the other tasks of the work package. These materials not only reinforced the theoretical foundation of the course content, but provided hands-on tools, practical examples and policy perspectives that are directly relevant to the course objectives and material. Additionally, key events were leveraged both as dissemination opportunities and as sources of new input to enrich the course with up-to-date insights and additional material, and community feedback.

7.1 Additional Materials

The following materials were developed within the relevant work package tasks and have been added to the course as additional resources (downloadable booklets, as optional readings), to support learners in deepening their understanding and broadening their perspectives.

7.1.1 “Guidelines & Best practices for Honest Brokers”

Description: This booklet²⁷ is presented as a valuable supplementary resource for learners, detailing the essential role of Honest Brokers in the Open Science ecosystem, and providing additional information on the mediation process, its challenges and opportunities. Derived from deliverable *D3.3 Guidelines and Best Practices for Honest Brokers*²⁸, it provides insights into how Honest Brokers can effectively bridge the gap between scientific research and policy-making. Some Key Highlights include:

- **Understanding Honest Brokers:** Explore the definition and significance of Honest Brokers as neutral intermediaries who ensure that decision-makers have access to reliable and relevant scientific evidence.

²⁷ Locati, M., Tanlongo, F., Evangelinou, B., Dotta, G., COCCO, M., & CACCIAGUERRA, S. (2025). Guidelines and best practices for Honest Brokers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14712238>

²⁸ Locati, M., Tanlongo, F., Evangelinou, B., Dotta, G., Cocco, M., & Cacciaguerra, S. (2023). D3.3 Guidelines and best practices for Honest Brokers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14800423>

- **Challenges for Honest Brokers and other science mediators:** Learn about the obstacles Honest Brokers face, such as accessing trustworthy information and navigating uncertainties, and how Open Science can help address these issues.
- **Best Practices and Ethical Conduct:** Review guidelines covering ethical considerations, communication skills, and legal aspects critical for the effective functioning of Honest Brokers.
- **Integration of AI Tools:** Understand the impact of artificial intelligence on the role of Honest Brokers and how it can enhance their ability to perform their role and support effective decision-making processes.

The Open Science movement aims to democratise research by emphasising accessibility, transparency, and collaboration. This booklet not only supports Honest Brokers in their vital function, but also encourages researchers to adopt Open Science principles, ultimately promoting integrity and efficacy in scientific endeavours within public decision-making.

Authors: Mario Locati, Federica Tanlongo, Betty Evangelinou, Giulia Dotta, Massimo Cocco, Stefano Cacciaguerra

Figure 4: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Guidelines and Best Practices for Honest Brokers"

7.1.2 “Science4Policy kit for Competence Centres”

Description: The Science4Policy Kit²⁹, outcome of deliverable D3.4 *Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres*³⁰, is a practical resource offering real-life examples of Science4Policy initiatives, providing a rich repository of diverse case studies for Competence Centres to include in training activities, or to inspire similar initiatives in their local contexts. The Science4Policy Kit was created using a dual approach combining landscaping and survey methodologies to gather data on Science4Policy initiatives across multiple countries. These initiatives were categorised into ten distinct types, with representative examples featured in the Science4Policy Kit, highlighting practical tools and successful methodologies which serve as an inspiration for integrating science into policy-making processes.

Authors: Agnes Jasinska, Lottie Provost, Betty Evangelinou, Emma Lazzeri, Fotis Mystakopoulos, Daniel Turner, Georgios Psathas

Figure 5: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres"

²⁹ Jasinska, A., Provost, L., Evangelinou, B., Lazzeri, E., Mystakopoulos, F., Turner, D., & Psathas, G. (2025). Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14751412>

³⁰ Provost, L., Jasinska, A., Evangelinou, B., Mystakopoulos, F., Lazzeri, E., Turner, D., Psathas, G., Tanlongo, F., Rauste, P., Di Giorgio, S., & Prandoni, C. (2024). D3.4 Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14538239>

7.1.3 “Advancing evidence-based policymaking through Open Collections and Open Science Principles”

Description: This booklet³¹, outcome of deliverable *D3.5 Open collection case studies and related materia*³², is designed to offer policymakers insight into the essential connections between the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Open Science, and Open Collections across various domains. It highlights how global policy goals are intrinsically linked to research initiatives that rely on Open Collections to provide evidence for decision-making. Policy measures to develop collections as research infrastructure are making collections more accessible, useful for research and subsequently for evidence-based policy and impactful decisions. Relevant use cases demonstrate how Open Science and Open Collections are fundamental to achieving the SDGs. Future directions for developing and expanding the necessary Open Access to collections are also outlined.

Authors: Isolde Gottwald, Angus White, Clara Lines, Betty Evangelinou, Katrin Vohland, Heimo Rainer

Figure 6: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Advancing evidence-based policymaking through Open Collections and Open Science Principles"

³¹ Gottwald, I., Whyte, A., Linés, C., Evangelinou, B., Vohland, K., & Rainer, H. (2024). Advancing evidence-based policymaking through Open Collections and Open Science Principles. Verlag des Naturhistorischen Museums Wien. <https://doi.org/10.57827/978-3-903096-78-3> and <https://zenodo.org/records/14865795>

³² Gottwald, I., Whyte, A., Linés, C., Kiesel, M., Rainer, H., Vohland, K., Wildgaard, L., Souyioultzoglou, I., Di Giorgio, S., & Prandoni, C. (2024). D3.5 Open collection case studies and related material (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14244666>

7.1.4 “Guidelines and FAQs on Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI)”

Description: This booklet³³, outcome of the deliverable *D3.7 Coordinated set of guides, fact-sheets and FAQs on ELSI aspects for Civil Servants and Policy Makers*³⁴, provides training materials in the form of guides, fact-sheets and FAQs on ELSI aspects including but not limited to ethical issues, IPRs, Public Sector Information and Research Data, Licensing, Database Sui Generis Rights and Personal Data Protection. It focuses on general issues related to Civil Servants and Policy Makers, amongst other relevant profiles, like researchers, data stewards and legal and ethical advisors.

Key Highlights include: Comprehensive ELSI Guidance for Policy and Research, Essential Insights on Data Protection and Intellectual Property and Bridging Policy and Research Integrity

Authors: Kasper Drażewski, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Elora Fernandes, Emircan Karabuga, Thomas Margoni, Luca Schirru

Figure 7: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Guidelines and FAQs on Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI)"

³³ Drażewski, K., COLCELLI, V., Brizioli, S., Fernandes, E., Karabuga, E., Margoni, T., & Schirru, L. (2025). Guidelines and FAQs on ELSI aspects for Civil Servants and Policy Makers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14736425>

³⁴ Drażewski, K., COLCELLI, V., Brizioli, S., Fernandes, E., Karabuga, E., Margoni, T., & Schirru, L. (2024). D3.7 - Coordinated set of guides, fact-sheets and FAQs on ELSI aspects for Civil Servants and Policy Makers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14797142>

7.1.5 “Guidelines for Writing a Privacy Policy in Research Projects”

Description: This booklet³⁵ is a collection of useful materials for drafting privacy policies in research projects, informed by experience in coordinating and participating in both national and international initiatives. It identifies the most problematic areas in managing and processing personal data, offering practical solutions. The booklet includes forms and templates designed to be adapted to real-world situations and specific project needs.

Key Highlights include: Model templates for privacy policies, general and necessary legal requirements based on current legislation and practical solutions for adapting policies to various project scenarios

Attachments: The sections of the booklet include attachments with customisable templates and guidelines, covering the general legal requirements and ensuring compliance with data protection laws. These attachments are designed to be completed and adapted to meet the specific needs of different research projects.

Authors: Valentina Colcelli, Roberto Cippitani, Sabrina Brizioli, Alessandra Langella

Figure 8: Cover and excerpts from the booklet "Guidelines for Writing a Privacy Policy in Research Projects"

³⁵ Colcelli, V., Cippitani, R., Brizioli, S., & Langella, A. (2025). How to write a Privacy Policy in a Research Project. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14865812>

7.2 Relevant Events

Several high-level events provided important opportunities for disseminating course content, collecting feedback, and generating new material that was subsequently incorporated into the training. In more detail:

7.2.1 Empowering Europe's Green Deal: Open Science Skills and Taxonomy for sustainable innovation

This stakeholder forum, having taken place on November 6, 2024 in Brussels, was organised, under the leadership of the Natural History Museum of Vienna (NHMW), in collaboration of two Horizon Europe projects, Skills4EOSC and TETTRIs (Transforming European Taxonomy through Training, Research and Innovations)³⁶. The event aimed to provide policy-makers with insights into the role of Open Science competences in enhancing evidence-informed decision-making. A range of experts from different sectors were brought together, such as the European Commission's policy administration, Citizen Science, research and research infrastructures, funding organisations, education, and industry. With a specific focus on taxonomy, the panel discussions outlined how the Open Science skills can be used to support key policy areas, such as biodiversity conservation and the implementation of the EU Green Deal. Furthermore, several important aspects were highlighted, for example, cross-domain collaboration, training courses for FAIRification of scientific collections, Citizen Science and public engagement, as well as restructuring economic models.

The event provided a platform for intensive exchange and future collaboration opportunities across different sectors. The key outcomes as well as the booklet *“Advancing evidence-based policymaking through Open Collections and Open Science Principles”*³⁷, referenced above, were disseminated to further stakeholders, including scientific and museum

³⁶ TETTRIs Project website: <https://tettris.eu/>

³⁷ This booklet was designed to provide supplementary information to facilitate the discussion, and was distributed to all participants prior to the event.

communities as well as decision-makers, among them European Union parliamentarians and policy administration representatives.³⁸

Figure 9: Photo taken during the stakeholders forum “Empowering Europe's Green Deal: Open Science Skills and Taxonomy for sustainable innovation” panel discussion and setting

7.2.2 “Science4policy: bridging the gap between research and decision making” Workshop

The workshop “Science4policy: bridging the gap between research and decision making” was organised within Task3.5 of the Skills4EOOSC project, under the leadership of the University of Turin - Open Science Unit.

The workshop was a key component of WP3 dedicated to training on Science4policy, with a focus on researchers.

Communicating science effectively is becoming increasingly crucial in empowering society to take evidence-informed decisions to address its challenges, especially in the context of evidence-informed policymaking.

The workshop was intended to enhance researchers' communication skills and facilitate dialogue with policymakers by upskilling communication competences.

³⁸ Further details about this event can be found in: Gottwald, I., Kiesel, M., Linés, C., Evangelinou, B., Rainer, H., Ritschard, E., & Gänsdorfer, N. (2025). Round Table for Parliamentarians and PA in Brussels. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15209442>

The workshop took place in Rome, on January 30-31, 2025, with 50 professionals participating during the first day (theory) and 20 researchers during the second day (hands-on), from different fields.

A report³⁹ was created for the workshop, including key messages and lessons learned about each day, additional training material and insights from the participants. Also photos from the workshop are displayed within the report.

Figure 10: Cover and excerpts from the workshop report "Science4policy: bridging the gap between research and decision making"

7.2.3 IDCC25 Workshop: Open Science in Action: Building Skills, Crafting FAIR Resources, and Recognising Achievement with Skills4EOSC

This workshop⁴⁰ was designed to equip participants with the essential skills necessary for successful engagement in Open Science by taking advantage of the Skills4EOSC project outputs. Through interactive sessions, attendees learned how to use the Minimum Viable Skills profiles, develop FAIR-

³⁹ Giglia, E., & Evangelinou, B. (2025). MS3.3 - Workshop Practice of informing Policy through Evidence. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944937>

⁴⁰ Filiposka, S., Evangelinou, B., Green, D., Whyte, A., & Bjerde, K. W. (2025, February 21). IDCC'25 Workshop: Open Science in Action: Building Skills, Crafting FAIR Resources, and Recognizing Achievement with Skills4EOSC. 19th International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC), The Hague, The Netherlands. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14905897>

compliant learning materials, and employ a recognition framework to acknowledge and reward these competences.

In this workshop, the Open-Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making (EIDM) learning path was presented, as well as the development and certification methodology. After the presentation, a group activity was performed, asking from the participants to develop their own Open Science Training Plan. The workshop took place within the IDCC25 Conference in Hague, on February 17, 2025, where 40 professionals from diverse backgrounds participated.

Figure 11: Photos taken during Session 4 Group Activity: “Open Science Training Plan Development”

7.2.4 Science Advice Mechanism (SAM) Conference 2025

This two-day conference, also entitled ‘Building bridges: Shaping Europe’s science-for-policy landscape’⁴¹, gathered around 400 science-for-policy practitioners and researchers, policymakers at all levels, and representatives of organisations that regularly interact with policy, especially academies. It was organised by the Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM)⁴², which provides advise on scientific issues to the European Commission and other EU

⁴¹ <https://scientificadvice.eu/conference/>

⁴² [Scientific Advice Mechanism](#)

institutions. The conference took place on May 26 and 27, 2025, at the Austrian Academy of Sciences in Vienna.

Skills4EOSC participated with a 60-seconds pitch and a poster⁴³ on the trainings and resources for researchers and policy makers, civil servants and honest brokers, developed in WP3. The main topics included the learning path on “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” (EIDM), the Science4Policy Workshop and the “Science4Policy Kit for Competence Centres”. Three further publications were also presented, namely the handbook on “Ethical, Legal and Social Implications (ELSI) for Policy”, the “Guidelines for Honest Brokers” and the booklet on Open Collections for evidence-based policymaking.

This event allowed for networking and dissemination of all the diverse outcomes of Skills4EOSC, relevant for the further (re-)use of materials and resources after the end of the project. The poster was very well received by the conference audience, winning the award for “Most Effective” initiative presented in the poster session.

Figure 12: Skills4EOSC Poster won “Most Effective” initiative (right) and photo taken during the SAM conference voting process (left)

⁴³ The poster can be found in Zenodo under the DOI [10.5281/zenodo.15529507](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15529507)

8 National Pilot Trainings

8.1 Overview of the National Pilot Trainings

Following the completion of the train-the-trainer courses, one of the main objectives within this task was to conduct national trainings in each participating country. These sessions aimed to cascade the acquired knowledge in a local level, engaging relevant communities of decision makers.

The primary goal was to adapt and reuse the course material to meet specific regional needs of the communities that were selected by each country's pilot organisers. In the below tables, the initial plan of each country is presented, as well as the final actions they took. In the next subsections, we also provide an analysis per pilot, as well as a summary of the results for the whole process.

Table 12: Initial Plan for the National Pilots

No.	Country	Groups of Target Profiles (policymakers and civil servants, knowledge brokers, decision makers)	Expected size of audience (persons)	Estimated (month)	Date
1	Italy	Funding Org./Ministries/Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M30-M32	
2	Greece	Governmental Org./ Ministries/ Top level Research Performing Org.	15-30	M31-M33	
3	Norway	Ministries/Top level Research Performing Org.	15-30	M29-M31	
4	Spain	Governmental Org./ Funding Org./ Top level Research Performing Org.	10-20	M30-M32	
5	Denmark	Governmental Org./ Funding Org./ Top level Research Performing Org./ Ministries	15-20	M30-M31	
6	France	Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M31-M33	
7	Finland	Top level Research Performing Org./ Funding Org.	20-30	M29-M31	
8	UK	Governmental Org./ Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M30-M32	
9	Sweden	Top level Research Performing Org.	20-30	M30-M32	
10	Netherlands	Funding Org./ Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M30-M32	
11	Belgium	Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M29-M31	

12	Poland	Funding Org.	10-15	M30-M32
13	Germany	Top level Research Performing Org.	10-15	M31-M33
14	Estonia	Governmental Org./ Funding Org.	15-30	M29-M31
15	Austria	Top level Research Performing Org./ OS Professionals	10-20	M31-M33

Figure 13: Initial indicative timeline for the national pilots

During the organisation period, some details per pilot were modified and became more concrete, based on the actual needs of the audiences of each country. Below you can see, in a summary, the new structure of the national pilots, as they were conducted per country.

Table 13: Actual Structure of National Pilots

No.	Country	Title of Training	Target Audience	No. of part.	Location	Duration	Actual Date	Language
1	Finland (CSC)	Research data management skills as a future success factor + The importance of Open Science and responsible evaluation of research	Funders, university leaders and research administrators	ap. 41 + 26 participants	In person - Conference presentation	0.5 hours + 1.5 hours	12/08/2024 + 21/05/2025	Finnish lang, mixed pres.
2	France (AMU)	Open Science Training for "decision-makers"	Managers, service directors, research directors	ap. 12 participants	In person - Workshop	1 full day	21/03/2025	French lang. and pres.
3	Spain (UC3M)	Coalition for Advancing Research	Researchers, research managers,	ap. 40 participants	In person - Presentation	2 hours/day	27-28/03/2025	Spanish lang. and

		Assessment: CoARA	institutional leaders from Centres of Excellence accr. by the Xunta de Galicia	participants	tions + Discussion			pres.
4	Denmark (CBS) 	FAIR Data as a Strategic Asset + Towards a National Competence Centre for FAIR and Open Science Skills	Researchers, research support staff, decision-makers from the Danish universities, funders, representatives of the Ministry for Higher Education and Research, research infrastructure providers	ap. 40+ 26 participants	In person - Workshop with Presentations and Discussions	7 hours + 4 hours	05/03/2025 & 12/05/2025	Danish/English lang. English pres.
5	Austria (NHMW) 	The Importance of Scientific Collections and Open Science Skills for Policy, Culture, Science, and Arts in Austria	policy makers, honest brokers, civil servants	ap. 40 participants	Online Webinar + Discussion	1.5 hours	08/04/2025	German lang. and pres.
6	Sweden (Chalmers) 	Skills4EOOSC: Building competence in Open Science	Funders, Civil Servants + Research support, Policymakers	ap. 15 participants	In person - Seminar + Roundtable	1.5 hours	09/04/2025	Swedish lang, English pres.
7	Netherlands (TU-Delft) 	Open Science and Innovation in the Grant Funding process	Decision makers in the university (specifically related to grant advising)	ap. 13 participants	In person - Presentation + Discussion	45 mins	22/04/2025	English lang. and pres.
8	Estonia (UT) 	Kick-off trainings for research data management and Open Science competence network	UT administration, grant office, data managers, researchers, research support staff	52 + 58 participants	In person Seminar + Group work	2 days, 3 hours per day	23/04/2025 & 14/05/2025	Estonian lang. and pres.
9	Belgium (KUL)	Between Open and Science and	Senior academics, PhD	ap. 20	In person -	4 hour	05/05/2025	English lang.

		research integrity	Researchers, postdoctoral researchers	participants	Roundtable	s		and pres.
10	Italy (GARR) 	Science4Policy: How research data transform public policy	Researchers interested in Science4Policy	ap. 34 participants	Online Webinar + Discussion	2 hours	20/05/2025	Italian lang. and pres.
11	Norway (UiB, Sikt) 	Open Science Lunch: Research ethics and participatory activities - what do researchers need to consider?	Researchers, Research support staff	ap. 65 participants	Online Webinar + Discussion	1 hour	22/05/2025	English lang. and pres.
12	Germany (KIT) 	Fostering Open Science: Skills, Profiles, and Learning Paths for Collaborative Future	Researchers, PhD and postdoctoral students, Research Support staff at University and Library level	ap. 15 participants	Online - Workshop + interactive questions	2 hours	23/05/2025	English lang. and pres.
13	UK (DCC) 	Open Science Explained: Why it Matters and How to Get Started	researchers, research software engineers, open research coordinators, and policy-relevant university stakeholders	ap. 23 participants	Online Webinar + Discussion	2 hours	29/05/2025	English lang. and pres.
14	Poland (PSNC) 	Open Science - Open Opportunities. The Key to Innovation and Social Development	university leaders, research centres leaders, researchers	ap. 86 participants	Online Webinar + Discussion	1 hour	04/06/2025	Polish lang. English pres.
15	Greece (GRNET) 	Enabling Open Science: Policy and Practice Approaches	Senior Researchers, University/Research Centres Representatives/ Decision Makers, Research Support Staff (Uni and Lib)	ap. 36 participants	Online Webinar + Discussion	3 hours	05/06/2025	Greek lang. English pres.

In the below paragraph, a more detailed analysis is provided per pilot.

8.2 Country Reports on National Pilot Trainings

8.2.1 Austria: “The Importance of Scientific Collections and Open Science Skills for Policy, Culture, Science, and Arts in Austria”

The national pilot training in Austria was organised by the Skills4EOSC team of the Natural History Museum of Vienna (NHMW) as a webinar, on April 8th, 2025, and co-organised by the EOSC-Support Office Austria (EOSC-SOA).

The event aimed to present key outcomes of Skills4EOSC and foster exchange about Open Science developments in Austria. A particular focus was placed on training materials for evidence-informed policymaking (EIDM training), with emphasis on materials from courses 2, 3 and 7⁴⁴.

The event invited target groups related to the EIDM training materials: policymakers, civil servants and honest brokers, emphasising the importance of capacity building for informed decision-making and long-term collaboration between science and policy. The webinar was conducted in German, the Austrian official language. Accordingly, core information from the training content and selected slides were translated.

The event brought together a wide range of stakeholders, including representatives from major Austrian universities (e.g. University of Vienna, TU Wien, University of Salzburg), The Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG), ministries (BMFWF “Federal Ministry of Woman, Science and Research”, BMIMI “Federal Ministry for Innovation, Mobility and Infrastructure”, BMWKKS “Federal Ministry for Housing, Arts, Culture, Media and Sport”), libraries (e.g., Austrian National Library), museums (e.g., ICOM Austria, MAK “Museum of Applied Arts”, Ferdinandeum Tyrolean State Museums) and other scientific institutions (e.g., VWI “Vienna Wiesenthal Institute for Holocaust Studies”). A total of approximately 40 individuals participated in

⁴⁴ Prior to the event, all Science4Policy training materials were distributed to all attendees, as well as pre-registered individuals. The materials were not translated for this purpose. The course overview and instructions, however, were made available in German.

the webinar. Discussions centred on principles of evidence-informed decision making, the evolving European Open Science landscape, legal aspects of data governance (EU Data Strategy, PSI Directive, IP, copyright), and the implementation of Open Science policies.

Following introductory sessions and the presentation of the training materials, various institutions (BMFWF, BMIMI, BKWMKS, Universities Austria/Open Science Austria, Tyrolean State Museums, EOSC-SOA and NHMW) shared their respective statements on the topics of the event. Thereby, various ministries positioned themselves regarding developments in Open Science, as well as collection holding museums. Furthermore, Universities Austria, as an umbrella organisation of Open Science Austria, contributed to the discussion from the perspective of Austrian universities.

Participants highlighted the strategic relevance of Open Science competences for decision-makers and underscored the need for sustainable digital infrastructures, data standardisation, and GDPR compliant access to research and cultural data. Universities were underscored for their role in ensuring open access to research, while cultural institutions such as museums were acknowledged for their contributions to increasing visibility and reuse of scientific and creative content.

The event demonstrated Austria's commitment to Open Science as a foundation for innovation, societal participation, and evidence-informed governance. It reinforced the value of European collaboration and continuous capacity building through projects like Skills4EOSC.

At the same time, the event posed a challenge, as addressing the different perspectives on policy-making around the OS agenda of universities and extra-university research-performing organisations required careful planning and coordination. However, the diverse topics covered within the event and positively engaging with policymakers were considered successful. Moreover, participants highlighted the thorough planning of the event as helpful, as well as the event being very informative and including high level representatives' statements on the topic of Open Science. Looking ahead, exchange about these topics will continue within regular meetings called

“EOSC-Café” organised by the BMFWF, ensuring sustained engagement and progress within the Austrian Open Science community.⁴⁵

8.2.2 Belgium: “Between Open Science and research integrity”

On May 5th, 2025, the KU Leuven Centre for IT & IP Law (CITIP) along with the Open Scholarly Communication in the ERA for Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS) joined forces to organise a training workshop for top-level researchers and research policy makers, entitled ‘Between Open Science and research integrity’ and showcasing the new perspectives created by progressing Open Science on the understanding and ethical obligations of research integrity. Hosted on the KU Leuven campus, the in-person event served as a prelude to the KU Leuven 2025 Open Science Day⁴⁶, where researchers from the University and beyond would present their work relevant to Open Science, including among those also a presentation of the Skills4EOSC project.

Chaired by Dr. Kasper Drązewski of CITIP, the 5th of May workshop brought together a panel comprised of Johan Van Der Eycken, showcasing relevant best practices and research findings on behalf of the National Archives of Belgium, Wouter Vandevelde, Research Integrity Expert of KU Leuven DOC - Research Coordination Office, Prof. Thomas Margoni, Centre for IT & IP Law (CITIP) and Fotis Mystakopoulos representing Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS). As intended, the workshop brought together a diverse audience of around 20 participants, ranging from junior researchers and Ph.D. researchers to senior academics, including the Head of CITIP, Prof. Jan de Bruyne.

Among the main themes discussed at the workshop it was demonstrated how openness plays a role in fostering trust in science and scientists and how

⁴⁵ The materials, statements of various institutions and an executive summary can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15863648> (presentation), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15863739> (executive summary and statements of the contributors).

⁴⁶ <https://www.kuleuven.be/open-science/events/2025/open-science-day-2025-1/open-science-day-2025-2>

research integrity and ethics share many goals with Open Science – pointing towards the necessity for research and researchers to be perceived as trustworthy also beyond the stage of publishing a research paper, or making the data underlying the project available, ensuring that transparency is maintained throughout and after publication, topics covered in EIDM Courses 1 and 2. In this respect, links were drawn to the constructs of transparency and accountability, also referenced in the ALLEA code⁴⁷ as the obligation of every researcher – as well as the diversity of individual approaches when things go wrong and mistakes are made. The discussion covered the pitfalls to be avoided within typical remedies: while correction and/or retracting a publication are a common approach, the matter, how the correction/retraction is carried out, is quite another. As no fixed terminology and procedures exist for corrections and retractions across journals and publishers, the resulting diversity of approaches is a challenge to be accounted for – along with the social stigma of corrections and retractions still perceived as the consequence of fraud. One of the conclusions was thus that for researchers to be ready to correct their mistakes, it is important to normalise the correction of scientific literature.

Participants remained actively interested in the public trust dimension following the contributions made by Johan Van Der Eycken and Fotis Mystakopoulos, showcasing that while in theory, research data should be reused in society, in practice insufficient trust often prevents researchers from using data repositories, despite the benefits that they offer in terms of discoverability, accessibility and reusability. The lacking trust cannot be remedied without being transparent in as many general aspects as possible. In practice, this depends heavily on the quality and the content of the metadata; the responsible approach here is to follow the metadata schemes of the given community – also to counter the risk of researchers inadvertently making errors rendering the data unusable. This was showcased as should be an important metric for measuring impact: how many people come and reuse the data? Trust can be built by linking data across disciplines and ensuring protection of sensitive data, such as by providing ‘digital reading

⁴⁷ The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>

rooms' to provide secure access to the repositories. This links to another challenge: giving a new meaning to 'as closed as necessary', we have been receiving reports of research data – even EU-funded data – disappearing amidst political tensions, including the growing concern that disinformation can spill over from academia into wider society⁴⁸, further eroding public trust in science.

A related important stream of discussion was inspired by Mr. Mystakopoulos who drew lines to how the “publish or perish” culture incentivises misconduct, from data fabrication to subtle biases like p-hacking and selective reporting, creating questionable research practices that undermine credibility. He argued that these problems are not isolated but rooted in systemic academic structures that reward visibility over rigour. This creates an environment where agenda-driven research thrives, and transparency is often lacking. The consequences extend beyond academia, fuelling public scepticism and misinformation. Drawing on insights from the OPERAS report *Fostering Trust in the Digital Age*⁴⁹, Open Science was shown as a vital countermeasure, with practices such as pre-registration, registered reports, open data, open methods, and open peer review helping expose bias early, encouraging reproducibility and cultivating accountability. However, despite their promise, many of these practices remain underutilised, particularly in disciplines where their relevance is not always immediately clear. At the same time, he acknowledged that openness alone is not a silver bullet. Legal, ethical, and institutional barriers, like data protection laws, copyright concerns, and disciplinary resistance, must be addressed. Here, initiatives like Skills4EOSC play a key role, offering tailored training that empowers researchers to adopt Open Science practices responsibly and effectively. Ultimately, genuine change requires a cultural shift, one that rethinks how research is assessed and rewarded⁵⁰, placing integrity, transparency, and

⁴⁸ McIntosh, Leslie D.; Vitale, Cynthia Hudson; White, William (2023). Taxonomy of Scholarly Disinformation. figshare. Figure. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24566875.v2>

⁴⁹ OPERAS AISBL, Dumouchel, S., Töpfer, M., Caliman Fontes, L., & Delmazo, C. (2025). *Fostering Trust in the Digital Age*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14621383>

⁵⁰ Moher D, Bouter L, Kleinert S, Glasziou P, Sham MH, et al. (2020) The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers: Fostering research integrity. *PLOS Biology* 18(7): e3000737. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>

inclusiveness at the centre of scholarly practice. This includes creating space for approaches like Citizen Science, which broaden participation and strengthen the connection between research and society.

Wrapping up the discussions and pointing towards the benefits of Open Science as means of reversing the 'ivory tower', societal perceptions about science and scientists were also an important theme in the later part of the presentation where Prof. Margoni, one of the founding fathers of the Skills4EOSC project, was presenting findings from recent research on improving access to (and reuse of) R&I results, publications and data for scientific purposes, launched in the context of Action 2 of the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda and published as a report⁵¹ by the European Commission – DG Research and Innovation.

8.2.3 Denmark: “FAIR Data as a Strategic Asset & Towards a National Competence Centre for FAIR and Open Science Skills”

FAIR Data as a Strategic Asset

On March 5, 2025, Copenhagen Business School (CBS) contributed to the first of two Danish national pilot trainings under the Skills4EOSC project, a seminar on national FAIR strategy implementation. Held in Odense and organised by the Danish FAIR Strategy Working Groups, the event brought together approximately 40 participants, including researchers, research support staff, research infrastructure providers, funders, and representatives from the Ministry for Higher Education and Research.

The full-day, in-person seminar was designed to raise awareness of FAIR data policies and their implementation in the Danish higher education institutions. It also addressed research infrastructure support, funder

⁵¹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Improving access to and reuse of research results, publications and data for scientific purposes – Study to evaluate the effects of the EU copyright framework on research and the effects of potential interventions and to identify and present relevant provisions for research in EU data and digital legislation, with a focus on rights and obligations, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/633395>

requirements, data valuation, and information security. Drawing on content from the EIDM training courses – especially courses 1, 5, 6, and 7 – the event highlighted the strategic relevance of FAIR data as a foundation for both Open Science and digital research governance.

Participants engaged with presentations from all FAIR Strategy Working Groups, followed by case studies and a panel debate that facilitated discussion on policy implementation. A key takeaway was the value of in-person formats for fostering dialogue between researchers and decision-makers. Positive feedback indicated strong interest in continuing such national seminars. Organisers noted that the training materials were particularly appreciated for their practical relevance, and follow-up activities are planned as part of Denmark's ongoing FAIR Strategy roadmap.

Towards a National Competence Centre for FAIR and Open Science Skills

On May 12, 2025, the Danish Skills4EOSC consortium organised a workshop at Copenhagen Business School as part of the Spring Seminar of the National Research Data Management Network. This in-person, half-day event gathered 26 participants, primarily research support staff and infrastructure providers, to explore the potential establishment of a national competence centre (CC) for FAIR data management and Open Science in Denmark.

The workshop was highly practice-oriented, featuring presentations and discussions on organisational models for a CC, potential activities, and how such a centre could benefit from Skills4EOSC deliverables – especially from WP6 and WP7. Topics included the professionalisation of data stewardship, sustainable training provision, and how to align national efforts with European Open Science initiatives.

The seminar made extensive use of the EIDM training modules, particularly Courses 1, 5, 6, and 7, and was supported by presentations from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Aarhus University (AU), and The Royal Library (KB). Participants expressed strong interest in continued collaboration and viewed the proposed CC as a critical next step in institutionalising Open Science competences in Denmark. Feedback on the training and its materials was overwhelmingly positive, underscoring the

utility of Skills4EOSC outputs in supporting national coordination. The seminar was part of an ongoing biannual series and will be followed up in the autumn.

8.2.4 Estonia: “Kick-off trainings for research data management and Open Science competence network”

The national pilot training in Estonia was organised by University of Tartu Library Open Science team, in cooperation with ELIXIR Estonia network.

The objective of the training was to lay the foundation for the UT network of data stewards and, in cooperation with the university administration, to develop the university's Open Science policy and guidelines.

The training consisted of two events from which the first one (23.04.2025) was focused on Open Science, open access and policymaking and the other one (14.05.2025) on research data management skills and strengths of future data stewards.

The events brought together representatives of UT administration, grant office, data managers, researchers and research support staff, basically the stakeholders who are responsible for policymaking regarding Open Science or interested in these topics.

The library, as the organising institution, anticipated too few participants, but the number of interested people exceeded expectations, which shows that the topic of Open Science is really relevant at the university. Kick-off trainings took place in-person and were recorded by university television (UTTV), as the faculties' administrations were interested in its content.

Skills4EOSC "Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making" courses (1,4,6,7) made it possible to address topics for which there had previously been no in-depth local expertise.

The content of the trainings was presented as follows:

Day 1, 23.04.2025, 3 hours, 52 participants.

“Open Science and Open Access Publishing”, conducted by the library's

Director of Development, Liisi Lembinen and Open Access Advisor, Elena Sipria-Mironov.

Presentations:

- What are the key principles of Open Science and what are they aiming to achieve?
- How do EU strategies and initiatives shape Open Science policy?
- What support services do Estonian universities offer researchers for implementing Open Science?
- What are the options for open access publishing, and what tools and models are used for this?
- What do funders expect from researchers?
- How can researchers be supported in meeting open access requirements?

Day 2, 14.05.2025, 3 hours, 58 participants

“Research Data Management”, conducted by the Data Librarian Tiiu Tarkpea, and ELIXIR Estonia data managers Diana Pilvar and Heleri Inno.

Presentations:

- What activities related to research data management are currently taking place at the University of Tartu and in Estonia?
- What data management-related activities take place across Europe?
- What is the research data lifecycle and what is research data management.
- Summary of the questionnaires regarding the trainings of data stewards.
- Group work: Mapping the strengths of data stewards and their willingness to contribute to policy development.

Conclusions and future activities:

Since the participants held very different positions, their levels of knowledge about Research Data Management (RDM) varied, ranging from basic to expert. The actual data stewards have wide range of expertise about RDM and related topics. By sharing knowledge and teaching one another in the

future, the entire network can advance to the next level. Data stewards could become valuable partners to the UT administration in shaping policies.

The follow-up activities will include seminars on the topics raised by the participants, held either in-person or online. A list of data stewards is already created to facilitate information sharing, exchange of questions, and planning future activities, including suggestions and contributions about the UT Open Science policy.

Some first steps include sharing knowledge within the network and inviting experts from other European universities. Short, online and very focused sessions are preferred.

In their feedback on the kick-off events, participants shared valuable insights and expressed their expectations and ideas on how to continue the network's activities. A comprehensive list of topics for future trainings was created, along with clear expectations directed to policy makers and the university administration.

8.2.5 Finland: “Research data management skills as a success factor for the future”

At the Research Services Days 22–23 Aug 2024 in Finland, the CSC’s RDM Competence Center gave a presentation entitled “Research data management skills as a success factor for the future”. The presentation included the crucial importance of Open Science and robust data management practices to funders, university leaders and research administrators. There were 41 attendees present during the speech. A conference like this gathers just the right audience for our message.

The presentation highlighted the need for adequate resources and mechanisms to recognise and incentivise the contribution of Open Science. As an integral part of the presentation were the training materials developed by the Skills4EOSC EIDM courses in module 3 “Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation”, which provided concrete examples and research findings on how researchers perceive the lack of incentives, for example.

Presentation was about how Open Science and doing things together drives progress and leads to better decision making. The presentation also addressed the barriers to Open Science and how the lack of incentives affects researchers' priorities. Finally, we discussed how we can make a difference by changing the incentive system, working together and providing training in data management and Open Science.

The presentation generated interest and some questions and discussion at the end of the presentation. It's important when thinking on future trainings to make sure to provide always some new information and to be clear in your message.

The importance of Open Science and responsible evaluation of research

As a second pilot, CSC – IT Center for Science organised a training for the research funders of the foundations, on 21st May, 2025. The title of the 1.5-hour training was “The importance of Open Science and responsible evaluation of research”. There were 26 participants from different foundations. The idea of the training was to present Open Science practices for funders. During the training we discussed the importance of Open Science, how to promote it and how to make it relevant to funders. We also discussed the impact of research, responsible research evaluation and the possibility of exploiting the researcher's profile of openness.

The content of the training was as following:

- Why is Open Science important and how can it be promoted?
- Research impact
- How a funder can promote openness: openness and transparency as a fundamental principle of responsible research evaluation.

We had also an interactive part where comments and opinions of the participants were asked through Mentimeter application. An "openness profile" developed in the framework of the EU-funded GraspOS project⁵² was presented. The profile aims to enable the highlighting of the merits (outputs and activities) of Open Science in the researcher profile of Research.fi service.

⁵² <https://graspos.eu/>

Participants were invited to provide feedback on the concept and implementation of the openness profile, and in particular on its usefulness or usability from the perspective of the research funder.

Presentations of the training were using partly materials developed by the Skills4EOSC EIDM courses in module 3 “Open Science is Essential for Advancing Research and Innovation”, and module 6 “Participation in Open Science” and “Research assessment” as well as module 17, about “Barriers to Participation in Open Science” and “Responsible Research Assessment”, which provided information on how researchers perceive the lack of incentives, and how the impact of research can be evaluated, for example.

Many interesting comments were collected during the event, both through the Mentimeter application but also in a spoken form. Additional feedback was gathered after the event and it was overwhelmingly positive; the participants highlighted the value of the event, mentioning the “diverse perspectives, concise overview, [and a] good and comprehensive update on the topic”.

8.2.6 France: “Open Science Training for “decision-makers””

The French pilot was organised on March 20, 2025. This training was dedicated to decision makers from different organisations: Aix-Marseille University, CNRS, INSERM, IRD.

Objectives: The aim of the training was each participant to become aware about the Open Science challenges and be able to anticipate the managerial impact on their team.

Key Content: (partly from EIDM Courses 1, 4, and 6)

Introduction: Best Practices in Science

- The drift in publishing models
- The drift in research evaluation
- Challenges related to poor data management
- The need for best practices to counter these drifts

Understanding the Stakes and Values of Open Science

- Defining Open Science
- Understanding the key pillars of Open Science
- Understanding the practical implementation of Open Science through PNSO 2 (Second French plan for Open Science)

Knowing and Engaging with the Open Science Landscape

- Open Science rooted in public policy
- Mapping the stakeholders and tools of Open Science

Adopting a Global Strategy

- Anticipating or preparing the organisation's positioning
- Leveraging existing tools at the organisational level

Identifying Available Support to Seize Open Science Opportunities and Mitigate Risks

Language: French (both presentation and material)

Participants: 3 sessions have already been performed with 12 participants each. The participants were Project managers, vice rectors, laboratory's director, service directors

Modalities: Case study, situation scenarios, traditional workshop

The immediate feedback from the training participants was very positive and highlighted the value and need for future relevant activities.

8.2.7 Germany: "Fostering Open Science: Skills, Profiles, and Learning Paths for a Collaborative Future"

Background: The German pilot was organised by RDM@KIT, i.e. KIT/Library in collaboration with KIT/SCC (Scientific Computing Centre). It was held on the 23rd of May, 2025, with a total duration of 2 hours and 15 participants to foster Open Science skills and awareness. The aim was to equip researchers and support staff with the knowledge and competences necessary to engage with Open Science practices, policies and infrastructures.

Objectives:

The primary objectives of the pilot were to:

- Introduce participants to the core principles of Open Science and their relevance within the research lifecycle.
- Explore emerging roles and competences required for Open Science, both at institutional and European levels.
- Present structured learning opportunities, competence profiles, and certification options for developing Open Science skills.
- Facilitate exchange and discussion on local challenges and opportunities for implementing Open Science practices at KIT and beyond.

Key Content:

The session was structured into four main parts:

1. Welcome & Introduction: Presentation of the Skills4EOSC initiative, Open Science and FAIR principles and Open Science policies (partly from EIDM course 1 and 6).
2. Open Science Skills and Competence Profiles: Overview of the EOSC framework for Open Science competences, relevant profiles (e.g. Data Steward, Open Science Officer), and a discussion on how these roles relate to local support structures at KIT (partly from EIDM course 4 and 5).
Learning Paths, Training Opportunities, and Certifications: Presentation of available resources, training formats, and certification schemes, including the EOSC Knowledge Hub, the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Registry, and the KIT internal RDM training programme (partly from Angus Whyte, et. al. (2023, June 30). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2).⁵³)
3. Skillsets – a space to structure your training needs). A highlight was the introduction of the Certificate of Advanced Studies (CAS) in Research Data Management/Open Science. The CAS offers a structured, accredited qualification for professionals working in Open Science and Research Data Management, and was well received by participants as a potential opportunity for personal and institutional skills development.

⁵³ Whyte, A., Green, D., Avanço, K., Di Giorgio, S., Gingold, A., Horton, L., Koteska, B., Kyprianou, K., Prnjat, O., Rauste, P., Schirru, L., Sowinski, C., Torres Ramos, G., van Leersum, N., Sharma, C., Méndez, E., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101903>

4. Interactive Discussion and Feedback: Open exchange about experiences, current challenges, and support needs concerning Open Science practices in participants' daily work. Participants shared insights on infrastructural gaps, policy awareness, and skills development priorities.

Language:

The pilot was conducted in English, ensuring inclusivity for KIT's international research community and alignment with the European-wide scope of the Skills4EOSC project.

After circulating a feedback survey following the webinar, we found that most participants responded positively, praising both the relevant content and engaging delivery format.

8.2.8 Greece: “Enabling Open Science: Policy and Practice Approaches”

Background: The Greek pilot was organised by GRNET, in collaboration with two other Skills4EOSC partners, OPERAS and GFOSS, within the framework of the National Open Science Competence Centre (Skills4EOSC GR-CC). Held on June 5, 2025, with a total duration of three (3) hours, the webinar was part of a broader strategy to localise and operationalise the training material developed in Skills4EOSC and specifically the Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision-Making Training Course. By reusing and adapting selected content from the main course, the event aimed not only to educate but also to support national efforts in policy implementation for Open Science. Presentations were delivered by trainers involved directly in the Skills4EOSC course, as well as by trainers who had been trained through the course, ensuring a consistent and well-informed delivery of the material.

The primary purpose of the webinar was to build awareness and strengthen the skills of a wide spectrum of stakeholders — including researchers, decision makers, and research support personnel — in understanding and applying the principles of Open Science. The design of the event was intentionally inclusive, targeting participants from a variety of universities, research centres, and disciplines across Greece. This cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary approach ensured that the dialogue was enriched by

multiple perspectives, and it underscored the growing commitment within the Greek scientific community to foster a culture of openness, transparency, collaboration, and reproducibility.

Objectives: The webinar was designed with several interconnected goals. Foremost was the aim to introduce participants to the fundamental values and principles that underpin Open Science, as well as Open Science practices and policies, helping to clarify its relevance in today's research environment. Organisers also sought to provide concrete, real-world examples through case studies drawn from prominent Greek universities, thereby bridging the gap between theory and practice. Another crucial objective was to foster an engaging and inclusive environment for dialogue, enabling participants to share their experiences, challenges, and perspectives regarding Open Science adoption. Furthermore, the event aimed to strengthen the emerging Greek Open Science community by encouraging further networking and collaboration among attendees. Finally, the webinar sought to identify and articulate the community's training and support needs, which will inform the design of future capacity-building initiatives tailored specifically to the Greek research context, with the support of the National Open Science Competence Center (Skills4EOSC GR-CC).

Key Content: The content of the webinar was carefully curated to provide a comprehensive introduction to Open Science and its practical implementation. To ensure consistency and build on established expertise, most of the main material was adapted and reused from the existing Skills4EOSC EIDM training course, identifying the necessary material in different Training Courses of the Learning Path (Training Courses 1, 4, 5, 6, and 7 - Modules: 01, 02, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 19, and 20). The opening session focused on the foundational principles of Open Science, introducing participants to the core values of Open Science, example case studies, as well as the roles of various stakeholders involved in this ecosystem. The session also highlighted strategies for capacity development, emphasising the importance of building skills and institutional support mechanisms.

In the second session, the focus shifted to Open Science policies and practical implementation strategies. Participants were introduced to different types

of policies, with concrete examples demonstrating how policy can shape research culture and practice. Particular attention was given to the need for clear processes for evaluation, monitoring, and continuous adaptation of policies to ensure they remain effective and relevant.

A significant feature of the webinar was the presentation of two detailed case studies from leading Greek institutions, from invited experts: the Department of Pedagogy and Primary Education of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) and the Department of Medicine of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH). These case studies offered valuable insights into the practical steps taken by these universities to promote Open Science practices, including challenges encountered and solutions adopted. Finally, the effort to create a Draft Policy Proposal for Open Science in Universities by HEAL-Link, was also presented by an invited speaker.

Following the presentations, the webinar featured two interactive discussion sessions, which were designed to facilitate active participant engagement. These discussions encouraged attendees to reflect on barriers to Open Science adoption, incentives that could promote it, and practical actions that institutions and individuals could undertake to advance openness in research.

Language: The course material reused in the Greek Pilot was delivered in its original English version, reflecting the Skills4EOSC training course. Given that English is widely understood within the Greek research community, we considered important for stakeholders to view the original materials as part of their familiarisation with international Open Science resources. Nevertheless, the spoken narrative and explanations throughout the webinar were provided in Greek, ensuring accessibility and clear understanding for all participants. This bilingual approach balanced presenting the original course content with clear and effective communication tailored to the local audience.

Participants: The webinar gathered a total of 36 participants, individually invited based on their roles and expertise. This selective approach ensured the presence of diverse and relevant group of stakeholders, representing, as

possible, the Greek research ecosystem. As mentioned above, attendees included researchers from various scientific disciplines and levels, decision makers in their organisations, as well as research support personnel from universities and research centres. This carefully curated group enriched the discussions, fostering a comprehensive exchange of perspectives and experiences related to Open Science. The relatively intimate group size facilitated active engagement during interactive sessions, enabling meaningful exchanges and reflections throughout the event.

Outcomes: The feedback from the Greek Pilot was greatly positive, with participants recognising it as a very good and important opportunity to promote Open Science awareness and capacity building in Greece. Attendees expressed strong interest in more events of this nature and highlighted the need to involve an even broader range of stakeholders in future activities, including funders. There was a clear call for creating new events—both targeted and open to the wider public—to raise awareness and foster a deeper understanding of Open Science principles across the research ecosystem. The importance of ongoing collaboration and networking was repeatedly emphasised, with many participants eager to stay engaged and actively participate in upcoming initiatives. This enthusiasm underlines the value of continuing to build a supportive community around Open Science, ensuring sustained momentum and impact.

8.2.9 Italy: “Science4Policy: come i dati della ricerca possono trasformare la politica (How research data transform public policy)”

The national pilot training in Italy was organised by the Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (ICDI) Competence Centre as a two-hour webinar⁵⁴ on May 20, 2025. The language was Italian; the title means “Science4Policy: How research data transforms public policy”.

Since it was not possible to organise an event specifically for policymakers, due to other national events already planned during the same period, it was

⁵⁴ <https://www.icdi.it/en/events/webinar-science4policy>

decided to organise the webinar for whoever is involved in the research process, particularly researchers and research support staff, including librarians. The main goal was to provide participants with information, advice, examples and suggestions on how to interact with policymakers and decision makers, so that they can effectively promote Open Science and advocate for concrete actions whenever they will be in contact with them.

The instructors were participants in the "Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making" training⁵⁵, where they were trained and awarded with the Master Trainer badge. This webinar represented a first practical application of the competences acquired, as well as a reuse of the training material developed for the course. For their presentations they reused some of the original slides from the EIDM courses translated into Italian and slightly adapted where necessary.

The webinar was structured in two sessions with short introductory presentations followed by an open discussion driven by some questions/topics sent to the registrants in advance. Wooclap was used to facilitate the interaction among students and instructors.

Agenda of the webinar:

Session 1

- **Introduzione (Introduction):** Sara di Giorgio
- **La Scienza Aperta come nuovo paradigma (Open Science as the new paradigm):** *Paola Galimberti - Università di Milano, Mauro Paschetta - Politecnico di Torino*
 - **Cos'è la Scienza Aperta e come sta cambiando il mondo della ricerca (What Open Science is and how it is changing the research environment)**
 - **Discussione interattiva (Interactive discussion):** Esempi ed esperienze concrete di impatto della scienza aperta sulla società: riflessioni e discussione con i partecipanti sui contenuti che possono essere più efficaci per una comunicazione con i decisori (Concrete examples and experiences of the impact of Open Science

⁵⁵ The organizers of the webinar are, in alphabetical order (instructors underlined), Andrea Corleto (GARR), Emma Lazzeri (CNR), Ilaria Stura (University of Torino), Luciano Gaido (INFN), Mauro Paschetta (Politecnico di Torino), Paola Galimberti (University of Milano), Rossana Damiano (University of Torino), Sara di Giorgio (GARR)

on society: reflections and discussion with participants on the topics that can be more effective for communication with decision makers)

Session 2:

L'importanza del riutilizzo dei dati nel processo di Decision Making (The importance of reusing data in the decision-making process): *Rossana Damiano and Ilaria Stura - Università di Torino*

- **Introduzione: Come i dati aperti e FAIR supportano decisioni informate nelle politiche pubbliche (Introduction: How open and FAIR data support informed decision making in public policy)**
- **Discussione interattiva (Interactive discussion):** Analisi di casi d'uso e possibilità di interazione con i decisori sui benefici e le sfide del riutilizzo dei dati e dei risultati della ricerca (Analysis of some use cases and possibility to interact with decision makers about the benefits and challenges of reuse of data and research outputs)

Out of 57 registrants, 34 attended the webinar; among them 39% were research support professionals, 30% researchers at various career stages and 30% librarians (some of them also involved in research support activities).

During the event, several crucial aspects related to open data, FAIR data and the so-called "dirty data"⁵⁶ were discussed. It clearly emerged that FAIR data represent a virtuous practice: they allow a greater number of experts to access and use them for the benefit of multidisciplinary science; this also has a huge positive impact on their quality.

It was observed that open data can be misused (often involuntarily due to the inability to interpret them correctly by non-experts) and they may even be used to support conspiracy theories. This is for sure true, however one possible countermeasure is to contrast these theories with evidence-based arguments relying on the same openly available data. On the other hand, when conspiracy theories are based on closed or inaccessible data, it is much more difficult to offer effective counterarguments.

⁵⁶ "Dirty Data" are considered data containing inaccuracies, inconsistencies, or errors that may compromise their usefulness and reliability.

Scientific communication was another important topic discussed, in particular about policymakers. The key message from the discussion was the need to use adequate and accessible language and the role of experts acting as intermediaries to support a proper understanding of scientific data is really important.

Three key elements were identified in the process of making evidence-informed decisions:

1. The availability of quality data;
2. The role of experts to support interpreting the data correctly;
3. The ability of experts to clearly communicate the quality and limitations of data.

All these aspects are essential for effective evidence-informed decision-making. At the same time, it was highlighted that it is important to remember that uncertainty is an integral part of scientific knowledge and must be recognised and communicated as such.

Finally, the role of Artificial Intelligence was discussed. Although it is an extremely powerful tool for trend analysis and processing large amounts of data, AI cannot replace human judgment in the decision-making process. Furthermore, the quality of the results strongly depends on the data used in the training phase: if these are not reliable, we risk amplifying the disadvantages rather than obtaining benefits.

8.2.10 Netherlands: "Open Science and Innovation in the Grant Funding process"

The national training pilot in the Netherlands was organised for grant advisors and related decision-makers at TU Delft, an in-person event held on April 22, 2025. The session was conducted primarily in English, and the participants were 13 in total. The pilot was organised in a workshop/roundtable format, to focus the decision specifically on Open Science in the grant funding process, existing experiences and how to enhance them further. Materials from the "Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making" TtT course were reused to facilitate the

discussion, specifically Module 13 (Investing in OS), Module 11 (OS Stakeholders), Module 12 (Collaboration Strategies for Stakeholders), Module 02 (OS and Society), Module 03 (OS is essential for advancing research and innovation).

Focussing on a very specific topic (grant funding and OS), and enabling a discussion-based format proved very effective in getting participants engaged with the material. Short presentations (using the modules mentioned above) were interspersed with interactive elements, including Mentimeter and verbal discussions. The discussions focussed on existing OS requirements of Dutch and EU funders, and the need for consultation with OS- and RDM-specific experts (like data stewards) to help address these points in grant proposals. Grant advisors noted that they did not aim to become Open Science experts themselves, and preferred to collaborate with other relevant stakeholders for support. However, they expressed interest in having access to a resource base or self-paced learning units that would allow them to consult reliable information on specific questions or topics. It was proposed that this idea be presented to university stakeholders, with the aim of establishing a dedicated resource hub.

8.2.11 Norway: “Open Science Lunch: Research ethics and participatory activities – what do researchers need to consider?”

The national training pilot in Norway was organised as an event in the established seminar series called Open Science Lunch⁵⁷. This monthly, digital seminar series invites presenters to introduce a topic related to Open Science, aimed for researchers, librarians and support staff in research and higher education in Norway. Being a collaboration between the University of Bergen, University of Oslo, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, and UiT The Arctic University of Norway, the series have a wide community reach and serves as a low-threshold meeting point to organise and promote Open Science topics.

⁵⁷ <https://www.ub.uio.no/english/courses-events/events/open-science-lunch/>

The Norwegian Research Council recently announced that a research ethics self-evaluation is expected for all funding applications by end of 2025 (previously being an “if needed”-criteria). The objective of the training event was thus to relate the Skills4EOSC “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” training and course material to a topic that is of current relevance for the Norwegian researchers, framing the criteria and researcher’s questions in a wider context.

The event was organised by University of Bergen Library and the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt) as an open, digital seminar⁵⁸ on Thursday May 22nd, 2025, 12.00-13.00, on Zoom. The University of Oslo Library assisted as hosts of the digital space. The event was held in English to include participants with international background. The one hour-long program was divided in three main parts:

Following a general welcome to the event, Ina Nepstad (senior adviser, Sikt and S4E course alumni) gave an introduction to the Skills4EOSC-project, Open Science in general, and introducing policy to promote Open Science (about 15 min). Using the EIDM course material from Course 7: "Implementing Open Science Policies", and Course 6: "Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices" as inspiration and adding her experience as data protection officer, she related the course material to the current Norwegian situation and policy development. The presentation can be found [here](#).

Secondly, Gunhild Rønningen (senior adviser, The Norwegian Research Council) provided an explanation of the background motivation of the upgraded criteria from funders for research ethic self-evaluation, including the overarching ambitions and demands from the funder and society perspective, and more practically describing what is needed and expected (about 20 min). Her experience from research funding and research ethics aspects, including dialogue with researchers, made for a very informative session. The presentation can be found [here](#).

⁵⁸<https://www.uib.no/en/ub/177685/research-ethics-and-participatory-activities-what-do-researchers-need-consider>

Finally, the meeting concluded with an open discussion session with questions from the audience (lasting approximately 20 min). It was moderated by the meeting hosts (i.e. organisers), who facilitated questions both from the chat and the live audience. Most comments generally considered feedback and questions to the RCN representative, for example specifications of expected self-evaluation format and length.

The seminar attracted approximately 65 participants, indicating the interest and relevance of the addressed topic. As this was an open, low-threshold event without a sign-up process, the participant group is not followed-up to provide formal feedback after the event. However, immediate feedback through spontaneous comments and reactions in the closing of the event was positive.

The event served as a valuable link between the Skills4EOSC project, the Norwegian Research Council, and Norwegian researchers and support staff, and facilitated discussion on shared and relevant topics. The experience from organising the event and presenting the topics will align with the continuation of the Open Science Lunch seminar series and other training activities related to Open Science.

8.2.12 Poland: “Open Science - Open Opportunities. The Key to Innovation and Social Development”

The event “Open Science - Open Opportunities. The Key to Innovation and Social Development”, which served as the Polish pilot, took place on June 4, 2025. The event was held in the form of a one-hour online webinar and attracted a total of 86 participants. The audience primarily consisted of university leaders, heads of research centres, and researchers, reflecting a strong interest from academic and scientific leadership in the topic of Open Science.

The webinar focused on Open Science as a driving force for innovation and social progress. Participants learned the definition and pillars of Open Science, contrasted with the concept of Closed Science. The session addressed the legal landscape surrounding Open Science, including international treaties, national legislation and policy directives. Economic

aspects were also discussed, highlighting both the benefits of Open Science and the costs of maintaining Closed Science models. Additionally, the role of policymakers and funders in promoting openness and investing in Open Science initiatives was emphasised.

Selected modules from the “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” learning path were used during the webinar, including:

- Module 01: Fundamentals of Open Science
- Module 04: Open Science vs. Closed Science
- Module 06: Legal and Ethical Frameworks and Considerations in Open Science
- Module 13: Investing in Open Science
- Module 15: Open Science and Artificial Intelligence
- Module 17: Open Science Policies Support Open Science Practices

Participants expressed satisfaction with the content and format of the webinar. The session sparked an active discussion on the future of Open Science in Poland, highlighting the importance of developing clear legal frameworks and supportive policies to foster openness in research and innovation.

8.2.13 Spain: “Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment: CoARA”

OpenScienceLab-UC3M, responsible of the Spanish Competence Centre gave a specialised training titled *“Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment: CoARA”* was conducted by Prof. Eva Méndez (UC3M) on March 28, 2025. This training programme was addressed for experts and public administration professionals delivered as part of the GOSCI research excellence initiative (Gestión Operativa de Centros de Investigación de Excelencia). This session directly reused and adapted core materials and pedagogical strategies previously developed in the “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” learning path that Dr. Méndez followed, particularly focusing on Responsible Research Assessment (RRA), included in EIDM Course 6, thereby ensuring coherence across different target audiences while responding to the specific needs of senior research managers and policy actors.

The content was further reinforced through a closely related seminar delivered the day before, on March 27, 2025 to another audience: CIGUS centres network. The CIGUS Network (Centros de Investigación del Sistema Universitario de Galicia) is a strategic initiative established by the regional government of Galicia (Xunta de Galicia) to promote excellence in research within the Galician University System. This network brings together a group of top-performing research centres across Galician universities that have demonstrated outstanding scientific productivity, international impact, and strong capacity to attract talent and funding. CIGUS plays a crucial role in shaping research policy and governance in the region. The training covered Responsible Research Assessment, responsible metrics, and institutional implementation strategies.

In both training cases, a total of 40 participants were introduced to the current policy landscape surrounding RRA, practical tools such as narrative CVs and open evaluation, and were encouraged to reflect on institutional strategies to embed RRA and Open Science principles. This cross-contextual delivery approach showcased the versatility of the EIDM training outputs and their scalability from academic to policy and governance environments.

8.2.14 Sweden: “Skills4EOSC: Building competence in Open Science”

The national Swedish pilot training was organised by Chalmers University of Technology and the Swedish National Data Service (SND). The event was formed as a workshop offered during SND's biannual network meeting on the 9th of April 2025. The event was aimed at policymakers, funders, and research support staff. However, it was difficult to raise interest among funders and higher-level leadership, possibly due to the context of the event, although several of the attendees lead operational research data management and Open Science work at their local universities.

A total of 15 participants were present, including workshop leaders Jeremy Azzopardi (Chalmers University of Technology) and William Illsley (SND/Gothenburg University).

Since Open Science principles are relatively well-known in Sweden, the focus of the workshop was to present concrete outputs from Skills4EOSC (using partly material from EIDM Course 1 and 5 and Skills4EOSC KERs⁵⁹), and to explore possibilities for their use and integration in a Swedish context. This exercise provided a platform to discuss Swedish Open Science training in a broad perspective, also reflecting on issues with the Swedish Open Science approach when it comes to funding and national coordination.

The feedback received pointed to the need for coordinated Open Science competence initiatives and programs for OS professionals in Sweden. Although interest for such initiatives exists, and although current initiatives in the form of working groups and training courses contribute strongly to the development of OS competence in the country, more coordination at a national level would make the creation of training resources and programs more effective. The lack of funding was seen as a serious challenge, and the need for further conversation with funding organisations was also highlighted.

8.2.15 UK: “Open Science Explained: Why it Matters and How to Get Started”

The national pilot training in the UK was organised in partnership with the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI) project and the University of Southampton. The one-hour webinar was held on May 29, 2025. The instructor for the webinar was Dr Cerys Willoughby, a Senior Research Fellow at the University of Southampton. Dr Willoughby also attended the first round of EIDM trainings with Skills4EOSC in October-November 2024.

The webinar provided an introduction to Open Science. The session explored the core principles of Open Science, highlighting the role of infrastructures like PSDI in driving progress. The webinar, using partly material from EIDM Courses 1 and 6, explored how Open Science promotes accessibility, so that research is available to everyone and fosters transparency, collaboration, and meaningful discussions. In addition to showcasing successful examples

⁵⁹ <https://www.skills4eosC.eu/kers>

of Open Science and examining its impact, the webinar also offered participants an opportunity to discuss the practical steps that can be used for making science more open and explore ways to cultivate a collaborative research culture.

As the webinar focused on introducing those working within the context of the physical sciences to the principles of Open Science, the webinar was not limited to policymakers. Instead, the webinar was open to all interested in learning about the principles of Open Science within this particular context. Amongst the 23 participants, the roles were quite diverse. Roles included Research Software Engineers, Data Engineers, Researchers, Open Science Coordinators, Research Associates and Consultants.

The feedback received at the end of the webinar was generally positive. Participants indicated the usefulness of this type of session, particularly in fields where Open Science discussions are fairly recent. Subsequently, Dr. Willoughby expects that similar trainings, particularly around FAIR data in the context of chemistry research, will be held as the PSDI project starts to engaging directly with researchers.

8.3 Conclusions/Comparative analysis of the pilots

The national pilot trainings marked a significant step toward building national capacity for Open Science and demonstrated the adaptability and relevance of the training content in diverse countries and contexts. Below we provide a summary of the key insights and conclusions drawn from the implementation of national trainings process.

Table 14: National Pilots Analysis Summary Table

National Pilot analysis summary Table	
Total no. of pilot trainings conducted (initial KPI: 15 pilots)	18 national pilot sessions in total
Total no. of participants trained (initial KPI: 150 trained and 200 researchers reached with material)	approximately 640 participants were trained in the national pilots

No. of participating countries	15 countries (all participating countries)
Audience Profiles	Based on the training needs of each country, different audience profiles were identified: institutional leadership and decision-makers, funders and policy makers, research support staff, researchers at all career stages, policy-relevant stakeholders
Materials reused from the EIDM TtT Courses	Even though each pilot had a different format and scope, there were some topics from the EIDM learning path that were mentioned most; some of them include the following: Open Science Core principles, Barriers to Open Science and Culture Change, Open Science Policies and Practices, Funding, ELSI topics, Stakeholders Collaboration, Evidence-Informed Decision Making, Capacity Building.
Training Formats	In-person (11/18): workshops, seminars, roundtables, and conference-style presentations Online (7/18): mainly webinars followed by discussions and interactive elements
Language diversity	The language used during each country pilot varied based on the target audience and local context. There were three primary modes of delivery equally used: English only (5/15) , when the target audience was international or in countries where English proficiency was high. Mixed English and National Language (5/15) , where it was important to balance accessibility with the use of the original existing training materials. National Language only (5/15) , chosen to ensure inclusiveness and broader reach, and where English is not so commonly used (material was translated in the local language).

Impact and Reflection: The pilot trainings had both immediate and strategic impacts. Based on the needs of each country and their institutions, we can identify some key insights gathered during the national pilots, related to the following main aspects:

- **Awareness and Visibility:** The pilot trainings played a key role in raising awareness about the importance of Open Science, especially among stakeholders who were previously unfamiliar with the topic. The diversity of training formats allowed participants to deepen their understanding but also brought into light local challenges and opportunities, making the sessions highly relevant. Moreover, the pilot sessions increased the visibility of the project and all the Skills4EOSC trainings that are offered for different professional profiles, with institutions becoming more aware of

opportunities for adopting or integrating materials into their own capacity building strategies.

- **Capacity Building:** Each pilot was delivered using a training format specifically tailored to the needs and scopes of its target audience, ranging from in-person workshops and seminars to online webinars and interactive sessions. This flexibility ensured relevance and effectiveness across diverse institutional and national contexts. The use of local or mixed language delivery enhanced accessibility, while the modular structure of the content allowed participants to engage with material most valuable for their needs. Moreover, the topics selected for each pilot were carefully chosen to address local priorities and stakeholders needs, highlighting the importance of the training adaptability. Altogether these elements supported skill development and long-term capacity building in a wider in a national level for each country.
- **Network Strengthening:** The pilots brought together participants from diverse disciplines, institutions, and professional backgrounds, fostering new connections and meaningful exchange of ideas and experiences. These interactions created opportunities for dialogue, serving as a starting point of potential future collaborations. Moreover, the diversity of the audience enriched conversations and helped break silos between roles and disciplines, strengthening the broader Open Science community.
- **Feedback-Driven Improvement:** Such pilot sessions offered a valuable opportunity to gather direct feedback from a wide range of participants, that can be used to update the training content and delivery, such as interactivity, timing and clarity of material. Suggestions from the audience also included additional training needs and new thematic areas to be addressed in future offerings, highlighting the evolving nature of things and new needs in skills development.
- **Institutional Uptake:** The pilot trainings generated significant interest among different institutions, not only in engaging more with the Skills4EOSC trainings that are offered through the project, but many of them requested additional tailored training sessions, relevant events with discussions or potential mentorship opportunities. This engagement highlights the important potential of such trainings and paves the way for

embedding Open Science culture more deeply within research and decision making.

- **Policy Recommendations:** The discussions within the pilot sessions highlighted the importance of policy development in advancing Open Science implementation, noting that while some countries have made significant progress, others are still in earlier stages. To this end, participants emphasised the need for more coordinated efforts at higher levels of decision-making, as well as the importance of supportive frameworks to effectively address challenges and promote best practices.

8.4 Course Material reused in other cases/trainings

Besides the national pilot trainings per country, several lectures and modules from the EIDM training were directly reused in other training activities developed within the project. This demonstrates not only the adaptability and high quality of the material, but also highlights the value of building on existing, relevant content in different contexts and purposes.

Below you can find two Skills4EOSC courses that reused the material from the EIDM training, one basically structured based mainly on reusing the material from the EIDM courses and one using the EIDM material as a preparatory module to the main course.

8.4.1 Other Skills4EOSC courses

1. YAICOS⁶⁰ (Yet Another Introductory Course on Open Science): YAICOS is Yet/Your Another Introductory Course on Open Science: a self-paced course designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the foundations, benefits, challenges, and practical applications of Open Science (OS). Through engaging video lectures, curated resources, and self-assessment formative quizzes, learners can explore how Open Science principles are reshaping research culture across disciplines and fostering responsible, transparent, and collaborative research.

⁶⁰ Link to the learning platform: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=81>

This course is developed solely by gathering and reusing material from other Skills4EOSC courses. The purpose of the creation of this course was to create a totally beginners course with the important aspects of Open Science without creating again material from scratch, and to show how easily the course material in Skills4EOSC can be reused to create another course structure.

In this course, most of the lectures, quizzes and material included in YAICOS are reused from the “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” Learning Path, and they are listed below:

- “Challenges of Implementing and Barriers to adopting Open Science” - EIDM Course 6: Module 17 Lecture 03
- “The Economic Impact of Closed Science vs Open Science” - EIDM Course 1: Module 04 Lecture 03
- “Closed Science - A Historical Perspective and Negative Consequences” - EIDM Course 1: Module 04 Lecture 01
- “Open Science values and principles” - EIDM Course 1: Module 01 Lecture 01
- “FAIR Principles and their role in Open Science” - EIDM Course 1: Module 01 Lecture 02
- “Responsible Research Assessment Movement” - EIDM Course 6: Module 17 Lecture 05
- “Open Science Infrastructures” - EIDM Course 6: Module 17 Lecture 06
- “Societal and Economic impact of Citizen Science from Galileo to post-truth populism” - EIDM Course 1: Module 02 Lecture 01
- “Overview of the legal regulatory framework on Personal Data, Non-Personal Data and Intellectual Property” - EIDM Course 2: Module 06 Lecture 01
- “Personal data in Open Science” - EIDM Course 2: Module 07 Lecture 02
- “Open Science and Non-personal Data” - EIDM Course 2: Module 07 Lecture 01

2. ELSI Perspectives in Open Science⁶¹ (Learning Path for ELSI Professionals): The ELSI Perspectives in Open Science learning path was designed in WP4 as an asynchronous, self-guided workshop tailored specifically for ELSI professionals who work with researchers engaged in Open Science. Its goal is to foster a deeper understanding of how ethical, legal, and societal considerations intersect with Open Science principles and practices. Participants are guided through a structured sequence of learning activities aimed at helping them bridge the common gaps between legal frameworks and research practice.

The learning path combines self-study with peer discussion, focusing on practical challenges and solutions. The learning path consists of two main parts: the Preparatory Module 0 designed as a self-paced, individual study component, and the Workshop Modules (10 in total) based on collaborative, discussion-based activities and scenario exercises.

The complete content of the Preparatory Module 0 was developed through the reuse and adaptation of the already existing, high-quality learning materials originally created by WP3. The curated list of carefully chosen materials provide the participants with the necessary foundation to engage effectively in the subsequent workshop modules. With the aim of introducing Open Science principles and stakeholders, together with FAIR principles, ethical issues and legal frameworks, the Preparatory Module 0 is structured in 8 Lectures, each reused from the WP3 EIDM training materials:

- From EIDM Course 1: "Open Science is the new norm"
 - Lecture 01: Open Science Values and Principles
 - Lecture 02: FAIR Principles and Their Role in Open Science
 - Lecture 03: Fostering Research Integrity and Reproducibility
- From EIDM Course 2: "Ethical, Legal and Societal Implications (ELSI) and Data Governance"
 - Lecture 04: Overview of the Legal Regulatory Framework on Personal Data, Non-Personal Data, and Intellectual Property
 - Lecture 05: Landscaping Ethical Issues in Open Science

⁶¹ Link to the learning platform: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=48>

- Lecture 06: Planning the FAIRification of Data
- From EIDM Course 4: "Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies"
 - Lecture 07: Open Science Stakeholders
- From EIDM Course 6: "Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices"
 - Lecture 08: Challenges of Implementing and Barriers to Adopting Open Science

8.4.2 Additional Events/Trainings/Workshops in a national or international level

Additionally, various trainers and project partners decided to reuse material and integrate elements from the training into other events and capacity building initiatives they performed for their organisations. Below you can find some examples from UK and Greece.

UK: Partners from the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) based at the University of Edinburgh had two separate opportunities to use the training materials developed in WP3 for international stakeholders.

Firstly, in January 2025, the DCC was invited to train data stewards and other data professionals at the King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST) in Saudi Arabia. Welcoming over 100 participants, the training covered introductions to Research Data Management, Open Science and Data Management Plans. Using materials from EIDM Module 17, lectures 3 and 4, the participants were introduced to the importance of research culture in their institution as well as the barriers researchers face in implementing Open Science practices within research workflows. The materials were shared with proper credits to Skills4EOSC and were well received.

Secondly, in April 2025, the DCC hosted a group of 30 data stewards, statisticians and IT professionals from the four largest Latvian Universities and as well as leaders from the Higher Education and Science Information Technology Shared Service Centre for training. The main objective of the training was to equip these participants with the skills and knowledge in Research Data Management. During the two-week training course, DCC

trainers were able to introduce concepts related to Open Science via developed materials in the Skills4EOSC project. Discussions about ethics, personal data and its relation to Open Science was informed by EIDM Module 7. Additionally, materials from EIDM Module 17 were reused to address the barriers often faced to participating in Open Science and to reinforce the importance of culture change within organisations whilst implementing Open Science best practices. The materials from Skills4EOSC were shared with participants and the feedback over the course of the two-week training was overwhelmingly positive.

Greece: In July 2025, the National Open Science Competence Centre in Greece organised a face-to-face seminar in the premises of GRNET, with subject “Introduction to Open Science: FAIR Principles, Challenges and Practical Application of Open Science”. It was a closed seminar, addressed to professionals and researchers in the field of Open Science. The seminar aimed to familiarise participants with the core values of Open Science and explore how these can be applied across scientific domains, including fields such as the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). The session also included a focused discussion on the practical challenges and barriers that researchers often face in adopting Open Science practices. The seminar began with a presentation on the fundamental concepts of Open Science and the FAIR framework. Material from different courses of WP3 and WP5 were reused for this event. This introductory session established a shared foundation for understanding how these principles underpin responsible and transparent research practices. A second presentation addressed the distinction between Open and Closed Science, highlighting the structural and cultural obstacles that can impede the transition to openness. It emphasised the institutional, technical, and behavioural challenges that must be addressed for Open Science to be effectively implemented. Vivid discussions took place during this presentation, as participants had a few questions, the most prominent of them being, whether Open Science is being unnecessarily bureaucratic and creates new mechanisms of control. The final presentation focused on the application of Open Science and Research Data Management (RDM) in the SSH. It was an opportunity to reuse materials from the Train-

the-Trainer established from T5.2 as part of WP5. It explored the particularities of SSH research, including the diversity of data types, the methodological nuances inherent in qualitative research, ethical considerations, and discussed how FAIR principles can be adapted to suit the specific needs of these disciplines. Citizen Science also featured in the discussion when assessing the needs to make data open, and how collective projects can benefit from citizen's participation, a key proposition of Open Science, even if often neglected. Together, the presentations provided participants with both a conceptual understanding and a critical perspective on the practical aspects of implementing Open Science in varied research contexts. Participants indicated an appetite to attend further events in the future of similar nature to discuss the development of Open Science in Greece. The immediate feedback was that the event was essential, useful and informative and the agreement was that they would be willing to attend future events.

8.4.3 Future trainings organised/planned from other S4E course alumni

Finally, several course alumni have reported organising or contributing to events and trainings within their own countries and institutions, where they applied knowledge and materials from the training. These initiatives highlight the multiplier effect of the course and demonstrate the versatility of the material for adaptation and reuse across diverse contexts. The vast amount of content and the different content types and formats offered within the course, allowed for flexible and effective customisation to meet the specific needs of different audiences and settings.

Finland: 1) At CSC Finland there is an already existing a domain agnostic online course on RDM basics⁶². The plan is to create a SSH focused version of this online course where, in addition to the existing CSC materials and training materials from SSH infrastructures, the Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making Course Materials and the SSH Open Science Course materials will be reused.

⁶² <https://csc.fi/en/training-calendar/cscs-self-study-research-data-management-course/>

2) CSC's RDM Competence Center is organising a webinar in August 2025 for the so-called Data Support network in Finland to present the Skills4EOSC results & training materials and to encourage trainers to reuse the course materials. This webinar will be in Finnish.

Italy: The material from the course was used in a seminar⁶³ on June 25, that was organised at University of Milano-Bicocca. This seminar was meant to help PhD students and researchers to delve into Open Science history, practices and open issues.

Norway: Material from the EIDM trainings in Skills4EOSC was reused in internal sessions at the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt), including follow-up seminars with a focus on Implementing Open Science Policies from the EIDM Courses. Moreover, a presentation on Open Science policies was given as part of a seminar series at the University of Bergen.

Sweden: The Skills4EOSC Train-the-Trainers programmes have been highly valuable for the Lund University efforts in community building within academic environments where data stewardship and open science roadmaps are not yet fully established. In more detail:

- **OSCL - Community at Lund University as part of INOSC:** At Lund University, Skills4EOSC EIDM materials have been used as input to the newly established Open Science Community Lund (OSCL), which operates as a community of best practices and is part of INOSC. The initiation of OSCL was directly influenced by a member who participated in the INOSC incubator programme and brought back resources that were instrumental for kickstarting the community.
- **Development of Local Training Initiatives:** At Lund University, a dedicated group supported by university management is discussing the development of a new short course on Open Science tailored for PhD students and early-career researchers. Materials from the Skills4EOSC Train-the-Trainers courses will be used as input for designing this course.

⁶³ <https://www.sociologia.unimib.it/it/eventi/repubblica-della-scienza-galileo-allopen-science>

Contribution to the OSCARS-funded Project HOMEROS: Within the HOMEROS project (an OSCARS-funded initiative), early-career scientists in Greek Geosciences are receiving training in FAIR and open science practices. The project manager, who is now a Skills4EOSC-certified instructor, actively supports the data management team by recommending relevant Skills4EOSC content, particularly from the “OS and Evidence-Informed Decision-Making” learning path and the domain-specific courses (e.g. Solid Earth and Environmental Sciences). The project aims to support early adopters at Greek universities, and by training more people, new open science communities can emerge (with support from local university libraries), creating an indirect but broader impact of Skills4EOSC.

9 Lessons Learned, Best Practices and Next Steps

The development and delivery of the training programme on Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making offered valuable insights related both to the content needs and the practical challenges of building capacity in policy making. This section summarises some key lessons learned through the whole design and delivery process, provides recommendations for future relevant activities and highlights some possible next steps to build on in future activities.

9.1 Lessons Learned

Designing for Relevance and Reusability

A structured methodology, including the Minimum Viable Skillset Framework, the FAIR-by-design Methodology, and the Quality Assurance Framework, with alignment with ethical, legal and social aspects (ELSI), proved essential in the design and delivery of the training material, ensuring quality, coherence, and adaptability. However, one of the challenges faced during the development of the training content was the lack of existing training resources tailored to the specific profiles of the target audience of the course. This required the team to design a curriculum in a way to address these gaps in a meaningful and scalable way.

Given the diverse backgrounds and geographical contexts of the participants, the content had to be both pedagogically relevant and practically applicable across multiple audiences. The modular and clear design of the learning path and the organisation of the vast amount of different modules into individual but interconnected courses facilitated reuse and adaptation of the content, as well as integration into other training initiatives, both within but also beyond the project activities.

Balancing Flexibility and Engagement

An important lesson from the training experience was the challenge to maintain the participants engagement in a fully flexible, non-mandatory

learning environment. The combination of the self-paced format with shorter live sessions enabled participants to manage their learning according to their own schedules, but in parallel create a sense of community and interaction. This approach was particularly effective given the diverse professional responsibilities and time constraints of participants from different countries, including those beyond Europe. However, the voluntary nature of the course revealed a spectrum of engagement: some participants joined simply to access specific content, while others were really engaged and actively participated in all the course activities, motivated by the opportunity to earn a formal certification. This experience emphasised the need to support the learners autonomy, while offering optional motivation to help participants remain engaged, without applying pressure or make participation obligatory. Finally, the blended model of self-paced content and live sessions proved to be a very valuable element, as it supported different learning preferences and provided opportunities for clarification, deeper discussions, real-time engagement, interaction and networking, all while preserving the flexibility of the overall course design.

Streamlining Assessment Practices

The shift from manually graded individual assignments to structured, auto-corrected quizzes in the second round of trainings really improved sustainability, streamlined the assessment process for the trainers and supported self-assessed learning. Introducing limited attempts in a certain timeframe and randomised questions from a larger question bank also helped maintain integrity and encouraged more thoughtful engagement with the material, reducing the likelihood of rote memorisation. The participants' very positive feedback on the value of the quizzes and how they enabled them to meaningfully assess their understanding, highlights the importance of well-crafted assessments in supporting learning and reflection in a self-paced environment. Although the more complex activities used as individual assessments in the first round were no longer mandatory in the second round of trainings, they remained an important resource. These exercises, presented as group activities during the live sessions, proved especially valuable for the participants, as they offered interactivity and community

building between them, as well as ready-to-use, tested material that could be easily adapted and reused in future trainings.

Strengthening Community and Continuity

The course played an important role in fostering a strong sense of community, by encouraging collaboration, interactivity, shared learning and networking. Group activities, live discussions, shared learning experiences promoted peer engagement and the exchange of ideas and perspectives, something that was really valuable for the participants to connect across different countries and disciplines. As a Train-the-Trainer programme, the course brought together future trainers from many countries, who not only benefited from the learning experience, but also already began forming potential networks that could support their future training activities. These connections and experiences laid the foundation for ongoing collaboration, long-term networking and knowledge sharing, beyond the scope of the course and the project itself.

Promoting Reuse and Adaptation

A key achievement of the training course is the demonstrated versatility and adaptability of its materials. The content developed within this learning path was actively reused and adapted in multiple ways across different contexts. Project partners incorporated material into other training courses and activities, both within and beyond the scope of the project. Most notably, the national pilot trainings, that were organised by each participating country as a follow-up to the main Train-the-Trainers programme, served as an important testbed for reuse, within different audience needs and local settings. Moreover, course alumni also played a role in promoting reuse. Several participants informed us about including and adapting material in trainings in their own institutions and local events.

All the above initiatives highlight the multiplier effect of the course and its contribution to the long-term capacity building efforts in Open Science and evidence-informed decision making. This impact was made possible thanks to the broad applicability and accessibility of the course materials, provided in multiple types and formats, including slide decks, video lectures,

instructors notes, case studies, additional reading materials, and practical activities. Their modular and adaptable nature supported the participants to reuse, translate and embed them into various educational and professional settings. This flexibility not only enhanced the content usefulness for future trainers, but also supported the need not to “reinvent the wheel” and allow for ongoing reuse of already tested, high-quality resources.

9.2 Recommendations and Best Practices

Drawing from the training experience within the entire lifecycle of the project, below you can find some recommendations and best practices that could potentially guide similar capacity building efforts:

1. **Use a modular course design:** Standalone modules that can be reused, adapted or delivered independently can support scalability, flexibility and customisation in different contexts.
2. **Include practical examples:** Incorporate real-world cases and applied scenarios throughout the training to help participants connect abstract concepts with tangible practices. This approach enhances understanding, supports adaptation and prepares participants to apply knowledge in their own professional environments.
3. **Provide multi-format material:** Offer materials in accessible formats (video lectures, editable slides, instructors notes, open documents, etc) to enable easy understanding and reuse. Instructors notes with narrative are really valuable for participants, in order to follow the content easily but also prepare for future trainings. Video lectures also enhance engagement in a self-paced environment.
4. **Combine multiple types of learning experiences and engagement:** A self-paced content is always preferable for busy professionals in different countries, but the possibility to attend a live session that would allow for clarifications, interactivity, collaboration and community building is really important and recognised by the participants, without compromising flexibility.
5. **Provide additional resources for interested learners:** Offer supplementary materials, such as readings, case studies, and toolkits to

support deeper understanding and exploration beyond the course content. This helps participants personalise their learning experience and engage more with certain topics of interest.

6. **Include well-crafted assessment methods:** Design assessments that are meaningful, manageable and aligned with the learning objectives of the course to encourage reflection and knowledge retention. Use a variety of assessment methods depending on the structure of the course, to balance the learners engagement, practical use and scalability.
7. **Provide motivation incentives:** Offer recognition opportunities, such as certificates, badges, or other rewarding mechanisms, to motivate participants and encourage deeper engagement.
8. **Encourage Feedback:** Actively seek for participants' feedback at multiple stages in the development and delivery stages of the training, to understand the audience needs, improve course design and enhance the learning experience.
9. **Create a valuable user experience:** Design the course environment to be user-friendly, intuitive and accessible. Incorporate a variety of interactive elements, ensure navigation is straightforward, materials are clear and easy to find and the overall experience encourages continuous participation and engagement.

9.3 Next Steps/Suggestions for future activities (beyond the scope of this project)

The following ideas outline some potential steps forward for building on the achievements of the project. While these activities fall beyond the scope of the project and the current timeline, they represent valuable opportunities for further growth and impact. These suggestions aim to inspire future initiatives, such as through the Competence Centre network activities but also other potential collaborations, that can further strengthen and expand the reach of the project's outcomes. Some of them include:

1. **Create a trainer Support Network – Community of Practice** to foster a collaborative environment between different countries and Competence

Centres, where trainers can share experiences, resources and best practices.

2. **Refine and Update Course Content** regularly, ensuring that the materials remain up-to-date, include latest developments in the Open Science landscape and continue to meet the evolving needs of the learners.
3. **Translate Course Materials in different languages** to increase accessibility and inclusivity, and thus allow a broader and more diverse audience to benefit from the training resources worldwide.
4. **Support future training events** using the experience and material from the courses and delivery methods, facilitating a wider dissemination of knowledge and skills.
5. **Develop microlearning units** as shorter, focused modules using course material for emerging topics or topics of wider interest, to further enhance the learners engagement and skills.
6. **Create toolkits and additional readings** for certain topics of interest and provide learners with more practical resources and deeper insights, in different disciplines and contexts.
7. **Expand content in settings beyond Europe** to foster inclusivity, international collaboration and global impact.

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11 Annexes

11.1 Annex A. Evaluation Forms

Evaluation Form Questions for each course (questions 12 and 13 change according to the topics of the certain course)

1. How satisfied are you with the course overall?

- Very dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied
- No answer

2. Please elaborate on your answer above. (free text)

3. When reflecting on your experience in the course, how much do you agree with each statement below?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
The content was relevant.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The information was presented clearly.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The pacing was right (not too slow, not too fast).	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The activities were helpful.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The instructor was effective.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The learning environment was good.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Please elaborate on your answers above. Did any aspect of the course in particular affect your ability to learn, either in a positive or a negative way? (free text)

5. What did you find most valuable about the course? (free text)

6. How could we improve the course in the future? (free text)

7. Were there any related topics not covered that you think should be added? (free text)

8. Overall, would you recommend this course to a colleague?

- No
- Possibly

- Yes
- No answer

9. Please elaborate on your answer above. If you would recommend the course, what would you say? If you would not recommend it, what is the main reason? (free text)

10. Please share any additional comments or suggestions about the course. (free text)

11. Did you have the time to complete the self-paced part prior to the live session? How much time did it take you to complete all the content on the self-paced part?

12. Please rate your level of knowledge for each area below PRIOR TO THIS COURSE.

	Novice	Intermediate	Expert
Open Science principles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
FAIR principles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Citizen Science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open Science Applications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open Science vs Closed Science - Costs and Ethical Concerns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research Integrity and Accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. Has YOUR PARTICIPATION IN THIS COURSE enhanced your knowledge in any of the areas below?

	Not really	Somewhat	Considerably
Open Science principles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
FAIR principles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Citizen Science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open Science Applications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open Science vs Closed Science - Costs and Ethical Concerns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research Integrity and Accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. Please elaborate on the two questions above. (free text)

15. Which of the following best describes your current role? (Select one)

- Researcher
- Research support staff
- Policy maker / Decision maker
- Civil servant
- Honest Broker
- Research infrastructure professional
- Trainer (on data related topics)
- Service provider
- Other

- No answer

16. Other: (free text)

17. May we contact you to learn more about your experience in this course and your suggestions for improvement? If so, please provide your email. (free text)

Final Evaluation Form Questions for the overall learning path

1. How satisfied are you with the overall course series?

- Very dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied
- No answer

2. Please elaborate on your answer above. (free text)

3. What is the most valuable thing you learned during this course series? (free text)

4. How would you rate the structure and content of the course series?

- Excellent – Clear and well-organized
- Good – Mostly clear, with some room for improvement
- Fair – Could be better organized
- Poor – Difficult to follow
- No answer

5. How confident do you feel about applying what you've learned in your professional context?

- Not Confident at all
- Not Very Confident
- Neutral
- Confident
- Very Confident
- No answer

6. What could we improve in the course series to better meet your needs? (free text)

7. What additional topics would you like to see covered in future sessions or courses? (free text)

8. Do you have any final thoughts or comments about the course series? (free text)

11.2 Annex B. Highlights and Testimonials from course participants

Round 1 Quotes:

<i>Course Title</i>	<i>Selected Participant Testimonials</i>
<i>Training course 1: "Open Science is the new norm"</i>	<p>"Keeping the plan and the material of the course as it is, an idea would be to extend the period of time of the course. In this way, it might be more convenient for each participant to spend more time to get prepared and the discussions could be more thorough. Also, in my opinion, the course could evolve and become part of a university curriculum."</p> <p>"If you need to be at prompt of OS I suggest you to look to Skills4eosc course on "Open science is the new norm". It makes clear any concept related to OS and allow you to be equipped with necessary tools and measures to ensure implementation of OS in your own context."</p> <p>"It was perfect for beginners and well-structured, providing many ideas for future training."</p> <p>"The course is an overview of the key issues of Open Science with a training approach and I find it useful both for its subjects and high quality and its educational perspective. "</p> <p>"I have been working in the department of Open Science support for some time. We provide education and training about Open Science and its pillars to the community of researchers, academia, librarians so my knowledge about these topics is sufficient, but I learned about some aspects more details."</p>
<i>Training course 2: "Introduction to ELSI and Data Governance "</i>	<p>"The information presented in this course was interesting and useful, particularly the connections between legal and ethical aspects."</p> <p>"This course covered important, complex aspects of Open Science in a professional, detailed manner. "</p> <p>"The materials in each module are well-structured and relevant to the subject matter. The graphs (pictures) help for better understanding."</p> <p>"It's worth taking this course to get a broad understanding of the subject under the guidance of knowledgeable teachers."</p> <p>"I found the most interesting and useful the information connects with research data and copyright. I work as Open Science Consultant so my general knowledge about Open Science principles and FAIR principles is already sufficient, but it is always useful to see how</p>

*Training course 3:
"Introduction to
Evidence-Informed
Decision Making"*

other people present this information. Very useful was information about legal aspects and laws related to research data."

"I saw in more detail who are the people involved in the decision-making process and what are their specific roles."

"It was interesting to see some other aspects of policy making. "

"A lot of effort had gone into the production of the training materials, which I greatly appreciate."

"The course allows me to reflect on topics I had never thought about before."

"[The course] gives a broad and complete view of the decision-making process"

"Apart from Open Science Outputs, the other topics were new for me, so I learnt a lot. "

"I did not know the various actors involved in the decision-making process and what their role was."

*Training course 4:
"Open Science
Stakeholders and
Collaboration
Strategies "*

"I liked the clarity of the topics. Knowing how to communicate well is really important. Thanks to the activity on verbal communication of uncertainty, I learned which are the right words to use and what to pay attention to when communicating."

"Not all information included in this course was new for me, but it offered a look from a different angle. I appreciate the detailed look at the stakeholders. The shift of focus from open access publications to other aspects of research opening is important and I did not realise that so much before. The communication of uncertainty was new for me, I learnt a lot. Data visualisation was very well prepared - it is also something I do not deal with in my work, so it was very useful to see examples. "

"Well structured presentations motivate me to learn."

"It is important to know how to communicate with different stakeholders. Different audiences require a different communication."

"For people like me with a scientific background, they are used to communicating only through numbers and graphs. Instead, the power of verbal communication is also very important."

"There was a lot of useful and new information that can help understand how the communication between researcher and policy makers can work. It is important for anybody fostering Open Science to know about and understand it."

*Training course 5:
"Empowering the*

"I really enjoyed the part about artificial intelligence applied to Open Science. It made me think about how this powerful tool can be used

Future of Research with Open Science

in the field where I work.”

“The course was interesting and sufficiently detailed. Flipped classroom worked well.”

“A lot of information was known but the course helped systematize it.”

“The presentation files (ppt and pdf) were well prepared and well understood. The possibility of preparing the online activity in advance was an excellent idea, since it could help some of the participants.”

“I am probably underestimating my level of knowledge for these areas (apart from AI). It has been useful to think a bit more about tailoring the argument to the listener to convince of investing and capacity building. We do this all the time but it is useful to remind oneself of the need.”

“The part about funding and AI was perhaps the least known, and so the course was very helpful.”

Training course 6: “Open Science Policies support Open Science Practices ”

“It is a great course with modules that talk about all the main concepts related to the development of Open Science policies. The examples and the activities are well thought out and very helpful. ”

“All the information connected with analysing OS policy, supporting practices and challenges and barriers to implementation were new and useful.”

“The practical part was the most interesting for me, as you learn what actions and policies other European countries are taking.”

“It is a great interesting course with engaging videos and helpful activities. Doesn't take too much time to do it and the information provided is really helpful to put the knowledge into practice.”

“New things and subtleties can be learned in Open Science policies.”

“I had previous knowledge in almost all of the areas of the course, but still, I found the material interesting, informative, and well-structured and consolidated. A great resource to organise local training and for further examples to put things into practice.”

Training course 7: “Implementing Open Science Policies ” and Overall evaluation of the Learning Path

“In addition to implementing an Open Science policy, I found the topic of evaluating the effects of Open Science policy on the research community and on their research activity very interesting.”

“I personally found the course very informative and I found that it builds very well on Course 6. I enjoyed the self-paced activities because they really made me think in a practical way.”

“I enjoyed the fact that the course includes policy development at different levels, e.g., universities, institutes, nations. I think it

	<p>enriches the course's content.”</p> <p>“Adapt policies based on new evidence and changing circumstances: now I have the tools to do this activity.”</p> <p>“The discussions about personal experiences of the instructors because I think they really bring something more to the table, sort of in the form of "lesson learned" from those who have already gone through some of the processes we learn on the course.”</p> <p>“Really useful pre-course organisation and very helpful team to troubleshoot any issues. The most valuable thing for me was spending time thinking about the bigger 'national/international' picture and how this can affect decision and what we are doing locally. Excellent material made available as well, to go back to when required.”</p> <p>“I think it is a valuable course for beginners who work in a research policy environment. The materials are varied and the self-paced activities means that anyone can choose when to study the pre-course material, without imposed times.”</p> <p>“I had never faced Open Science Policies Evaluation and Monitoring and Open Science Policies Adaptation.”</p>
<p><i>Overall Course Series Evaluation - EIDM Learning Path</i></p>	<p>“The content was useful and diverse and it was easy to see that a lot of effort had been put into it. I also liked the fact that a lot of different teaching methods had been used, e.g. ppt, videos, texts, activities, etc. The cooperation between the trainers clearly worked well.”</p> <p>“For me, the most interesting things during the entire course were the assignments.”</p> <p>“Real life examples and graphs and statistics.”</p> <p>“To learn about the best practices. “</p> <p>“Magnificent work!!! I really appreciate the tremendous amount of effort put into this venture by the whole team. “</p> <p>“Thank you very much, good information package!”</p>

Round 2 Quotes:

<i>Course Title</i>	<i>Selected Participant Testimonials</i>
<p><i>Training course 1: “Open Science is the new norm”</i></p>	<p>“I truly enjoyed this course and found it extremely valuable. The content was well-structured, up-to-date, and clearly aligned with current Open Science practices. I found very helpful the practical examples that reinforce the theoretical aspects.”</p> <p>“The course provided a good overview of Open Science and its</p>

*Training course 2:
"Introduction to
ELSI and Data
Governance "*

benefits. I had some awareness of the contents but I enjoyed reading more real-world examples and testing my knowledge with the quizzes. The live session provided a good opportunity to start meeting and knowing other people who are interested in the topic."

"I was extremely satisfied with the structure of the course and the diversity of information provided. I also highly appreciate the practical examples, the enthusiasm/engagement of the organizers/moderators and their readiness of them to provide us with additional information and resources. I am also glad that the course is part of a series that will provide us with deeper knowledge about different aspects of OS. It was excellent as an introductory module. And - last but not least - I also liked the fact that the tests required some thinking about the acquired knowledge (they were not purely fact-checking quizzes)."

"I am glad that it is possible to download the presentation and the transcription of the reading text. This will allow me to prepare materials for work and training of others."

"The live session might (beforehand) be expected to be a bit "redundant" with respect to the self-paced part, but instead both the recap of the main contents helped us to refresh them quickly and effectively, and the discussions - with the double possible path (chat and microphone) - were interesting, helped letting possibly new issues "emerge", and also the initial ice-breaking part was useful in giving us a view of the variety of scientific disciplines which may be interested in Open Science."

"The course delivers complex ethical and legal topics in a structured and digestible way, making it accessible even for those who are new to ELSI and data governance."

"The course was very well designed and culminated with the online session including group activities. I found such recaps with interactions between the trainers and the participants extremely useful."

"I like the practical aspects/examples that were included and the construction of tests that required some reflection on the presented material."

"It is a good opportunity to get a comprehensive overview of the issues that we will probably encounter while doing research and handling personal data. It provides several aspects to take into account regarding data management."

"A compact and useful package of knowledge on ELSI and Data Governance basics."

*Training course 3:
"Introduction to
Evidence-Informed
Decision Making"*

"This course has been very good for me because it allowed me to acquire new knowledge that I didn't have before, especially in topics like data science, evidence-based policy, and public health. What I learned is very useful and necessary to apply in my institution, as it is becoming increasingly important to make decisions based on real and well-analysed data. Additionally, it helped me better understand how to use tools that support informed decision-making and how to visualize data to communicate results more effectively. Without a doubt, it was a course that gave me great value and provided practical tools I can use in my work."

"Thoroughly presented crucial concepts and mechanisms constituting evidence making process, engaging activities, informative and handy materials were distributed."

"It's great introduction for both the governmental agencies and other actors that might not be aware of their agency in the policy making. The course empowers every party with the crucial understanding of the roles and responsibilities in the evidence-informed decision making."

"I would recommend the course to anyone interested in learning how to make decisions based on reliable evidence. It's especially useful for professionals in fields such as policy-making, healthcare, education, and research, as well as anyone looking to improve their critical thinking and decision-making skills."

"I will recommend the course in particular to researchers, to have a first overview of what EIDM means and to reflect on how they can improve their abilities in influencing political decision."

*Training course 4:
"Open Science
Stakeholders and
Collaboration
Strategies "*

"I find the content of the course very complete and full of examples that help the reader/student/future learner, to understand and put in place all the situations described."

"I found the section on communicating uncertainty extremely interesting. I found particularly engaging the discussion on the benefits of communicating uncertainty to different stakeholders: I think it's a topic not often included in the discussion with students."

"The course was very well prepared and conducted (with enthusiasm - which is important and contagious :). I feel I have learned a lot and managed to structure my existing knowledge about the subject."

"Presentations with a lot of material and additional links for further reading, testing my knowledge that required some reflection, not just fact checking, the live session summing up the course with

*Training course 5:
"Empowering the
Future of Research
with Open Science"*

recordings available later."

"I would recommend it as I believe communication, the creation of collaborative environments and communicating uncertainty are essential in today's research landscape. In particular, some colleagues may still reel at the thought of having to communicate their uncertainty on a research topic."

"I would definitely recommend this course to colleagues or professionals working in public policy, research, or digital transformation. It offers a well-balanced introduction to Artificial Intelligence and Open Science, combining technical concepts, ethical frameworks, and real-world applications. "

"What I found most valuable about the course was its balanced integration of theoretical foundations and real-world applications. The way it addressed the ethical dimensions of AI, along with practical case studies in policy-making and Open Science, made the content not only informative but also applicable. "

"I liked the fact that in the live session there were several different interactive activities, i.e. the high "relative weight" of the interactive part (questions from the audience, the breakout room activities...) with respect to the recap of the self-paced-part presentations. In my opinion, this format provides more "added value" to people participating in the live session, who are indeed expected to have already followed the self-paced part."

"I thoroughly enjoyed Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science. The course materials were well-structured, clear and engaging. The content provided a comprehensive overview and I especially appreciated the real-world examples and interactive elements, which made complex topics more accessible. Overall, this course was both inspiring and informative - highly recommended for anyone interested in the future of research."

*Training course 6:
"Open Science
Policies support
Open Science
Practices "*

"I've learnt a lot of concepts in this course about the different approaches of OS and the benefits of its practice. Every module has helped me to identify new aspects to take into account when implementing OS procedures. I found very useful the models and practices proposed by the instructors."

"The course provided extensive knowledge and practical tips (provided by highly professional instructors) reg. its subject. It has also enabled experience sharing among the participants."

"I would recommend this course because it is well-structured, accessible, and highly relevant for anyone working in research, education, or science policy who aims to effectively implement Open Science practices."

*Training course 7:
"Implementing
Open Science
Policies " and
Overall evaluation
of the Learning
Path*

"Policy-making is completely new to me, so I learned a lot. I was already aware of the barriers to implement OS, but I still learned something, in particular I now have a clearer list of areas to address when discussing OS and OS policies."

"Before the course, I had an intermediate level of knowledge on most topics, especially in policymaking, cultural change, and Open Science practices. However, the course considerably deepened my understanding, especially regarding the Responsible Research Assessment movement and the role of Open Science Infrastructures. The comprehensive structure and practical examples helped me consolidate concepts and identify areas of application at my institution."

"The course has considerably improved my knowledge of how to implement an Open Science policy. I now feel better prepared to apply these principles in my institution, particularly in adapting policies to our context and promoting stakeholder engagement."

"The course provided a comprehensive and well-structured overview of the development, implementation, and adaptation of Open Science policies. The balance between international frameworks and institutional realities was clearly explained, and the emphasis on community engagement and cultural change was especially valuable."

"I find the course subject very relevant and helpful. I loved the theoretical parts mixed with smartly designed assessments and live sessions with group activities."

"I may recommend the course either to colleagues who are specifically interested, in the context of their professional activity, in getting acquainted with the field of OS policy implementation, including for instance colleagues who are part of academic governance bodies at various levels, but possibly also to colleagues who are not involved in policy-making but already have some knowledge on OS practices (which means applying OS policies) and are curious about... "the other side of the topic", i.e. the ideas, points of view, challenges encountered by those who develop these OS policies. "

"I would definitely recommend this course. It provides a comprehensive and practical overview of how to design, implement, and adapt Open Science policies. "

*Overall Course
Series Evaluation -
EIDM Learning Path*

"Looking back on the entire course series over the past 2.5 months, I am very satisfied with the experience. The overall structure was logical and easy to follow, and the materials were consistently high-quality and engaging. I gained valuable insights throughout the series and hope to make good use of what I've learned in my

professional activities. "

"The learning path not only provides the fundamentals on the topic of OS, it trains you how to advocate for it and how to participate in the policy making. I think it`s a unique course!"

"Prior to this series of courses, I had acquired knowledge on Open Science, FAIR principles, data management, including practical/technical aspects (repositories, python coding...) but I had no knowledge about implementing Open Science policies. This series of courses has enlarged my competences in this field, integrating my previous knowledge with information on OS policies: the involved stakeholders, both general guidelines and more specific hints on how to implement and also monitor OS policies, and the involved challenges."

"I found the overall course series to be highly valuable. The content was clear, well-structured, and relevant to current challenges in implementing and adapting Open Science policies. Each module built upon the previous one effectively, and I especially appreciated the emphasis on stakeholder engagement and institutional context."

"Thank you for a well-designed and enriching learning journey!"

"Thank you so much for this opportunity!"